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ESIRA — ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS

Horizon Europe Grant agreement: 101136253

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REGIONAL REPORT ON SOCIAL EXCLUSION AND SOCIAL ECONOMY INITIATIVES IN RURAL AREAS

Gryfice and Leski-Bieszczadzki – Poland

Project details

ACRONYM	ESIRA
Title	ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS
Grant Agreement Number	101136253
Call	HORIZON-CL6-2023-COMMUNITIES-01
Project Coordinator	UNIVERSIDAD DE BURGOS

Name of the 1st region: Gryfice county

Country/NUTS-2 region: Poland/ Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship

Territorial level (local, micro region, powiat etc. + NUTS level if relevant): county

Name of the 2nd region: Leski and Bieszczadzki counties

Country/NUTS-2 region: Poland/ Podkarpackie Voivodeship

Territorial level (local, micro region, county etc. + NUTS level if relevant): county

Keywords	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social exclusion, - social economy, - social enterprises, - rural areas, - marginalisation, - Poland.
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To cite this publication: Katarzyna Gizińska, Agnieszka Kurdyś-Kujawska, Barbara Wieliczko (2024) *Regional Report On Social Exclusion And Social Economy Initiatives In Rural Areas - Gryfice and Leski-Bieszczadzki - Poland*. ESIRA project

Table of content

1.	Introduction.....	4
2.	Methodology	4
3.	Country overview: Poland	6
3.1	Territorial system of Poland	6
3.2	Strategies and policies	7
3.3	Territorial inequalities in Poland	10
3.4	Social economy	12
3.5	Social enterprises in Poland.....	15
3.5.1	Strategic framework.....	16
3.5.2	Policies/instruments/initiatives – supporting the social economy and/or social enterprises.....	22
4.	Regional overview: Gryfice region	32
4.1	Geographic and historical aspects.....	32
4.2	Demography	34
4.3	Economic situation	36
4.4	Labour market	39
4.5	Institutional setting.....	40
4.5.1	Local policies and instruments.....	45
5.	Vulnerability and social exclusion in the Gryfice region	50
5.1	Social exclusion and poverty	50
5.2	Labour market	52
5.3	Disadvantaged groups	54
5.4	Access to services	55
6.	Assets and potentials in the Gryfice region	59
7.	Conclusions and potential focus of MAP Zachodniopomorskie	62
8.	Regional overview: Leski-Bieszczadzki region.....	65
8.1	Geographic and historical aspects.....	65
8.2	Demography	67
8.3	Economic situation	69
8.4	Institutional setting.....	71
8.5	Policies/instruments/initiatives – local-rural development.....	74
8.6	Policies/instruments/initiatives - supporting the social economy and/or social enterprises.....	76
9.	Vulnerability and social exclusion in the Leski-Bieszczadzki region.....	78

9.1	Social exclusion and poverty	78
9.2	Labour market	79
9.3	Disadvantaged groups	83
9.4	Access to services	85
10.	Assets and potentials in the Leski-Bieszczadzki region	87
10.1	Social enterprises	88
11.	Conclusions and potential focus of MAP	90
12.	References.....	92
13.	Partners	102

1. Introduction

The main aim of this report was to collect information regarding the situation of rural areas and the communities residing in each of the participating regions in the ESIRA project (ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS HORIZON 101136253). These reports will act as the basis of D4.1, “Benchmark study on social exclusion in rural areas,” and D4.2, “Multi-level analysis of social economy initiatives in rural areas”.

This report aimed to go beyond the literature and statistical data available and, together with the organisations participating in the pilots, explore the regions' situations and the drivers behind the disadvantages.

The report introduces the territorial organization of Poland and analyses the situation of people living in rural areas, focusing on territorial inequalities.

A deeper examination of the drivers of vulnerability and social exclusion in rural contexts was done in the poviats. The analysis considers the social processes in the region and the livelihood opportunities at the municipal level. Existing assets and hidden resources in the commune were assessed according to statistical data and the opinions of the leading local social economy stakeholders.

2. Methodology

The following report synthesizes the findings of research conducted on two MAP regions. Given that the Gryfice and Leski-Bieszczadzki regions are situated within Poland, the national-level outlook is consistent across both regions. However, the local research components were addressed separately.

The regional report of the Leski-Bieszczadzki MAP has been produced using a mixed, complementary methodology, as this gives us a chance to go below the level of declarations and learn more about the researched phenomena, initiatives, and motivations behind the action. The key source of information was data obtained through qualitative methods (participatory and non-participatory observation, individual interviews, group interview with MAP members, content analysis of local websites and Facebook). Quantitative data were also included in the qualitative data, mainly from the reports of the Central Statistical Office¹ and the Statistical Office in Rzeszów². The Local Data Bank³ and the Samorządowe Vadamecum Samorządowca⁴ were also of great help. All the above sources are reliable, maintained by the most important state institution collecting statistical data in Poland. Some of the data was also obtained from the website ‘Polska w liczbach’⁵, as it presents data in a quick and accessible way; however, it is not a website run by a scientific/government institution, so data from it was cross-checked by the author also on the websites mentioned above. A good source of data shown in the form of maps was the 2023 publication by Monika Stanny, Andrzej Rosner and Łukasz

¹ <https://stat.gov.pl>

² <https://rzeszow.stat.gov.pl>

³ <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/bdl>

⁴ <https://svs.stat.gov.pl>

⁵ <https://www.polskawliczbach.pl>

Komorowski entitled 'Monitoring Rural Development'⁶. The above monitoring is a research project carried out by the European Fund for the Development of the Polish Countryside Foundation until 2012, carried out jointly with the Institute of Rural and Agricultural Development of the Polish Academy of Sciences. What is a great advantage in it is the presentation of data at the level of communes.

To develop the regional report of the Zachodniopomorskie MAP, mixed methods were used. It is a methodology that collects, analyses and integrates both quantitative and qualitative data. The research used a sequential approach that involves the collection and analysis of quantitative data, followed by the collection and analysis of qualitative data. Emphasis is placed on quantitative data, and the findings are taken into account in the interpretation phase of the data analysis. The main sources of quantitative data include:

- Reports prepared by Statistics Poland,
- Reports of the Statistical Office in Szczecin,
- Local Data Bank (one of the data banks elaborated by Statistics Poland),
- Reports and studies of the Regional Labour Office in Szczecin and the Powiat Labour Office in Gryfice,
- Reports and analyses published on the eRegion website⁷,
- Data from the Poland website in numbers⁸,
- Data from the Local Development Monitor website⁹,
- Development strategies: national, voivodeship and powiat levels.

The qualitative methods employed in the study encompass individual and group interviews with representatives of the Gryfice *gmina* (commune) and employees of social economy entities.

The part concerning the national level was based on desk research and was focused mainly on legal and policy documents and statistical data, mainly data offered by Statistics Poland (Główny Urząd Statystyczny – GUS).

The MAPs areas were previously engaged in a European project SHERPA (H2020). During this project a lot of qualitative data were acquired, numerous contacts were made, and relationships were built with various individuals, organisations and institutions - representatives of local NGOs, local government, entrepreneurs, activists or just 'ordinary' residents.

⁶ Stage IV Decade of socio-economic change (full version): <https://efrwp.pl/raporty-i-analizy/montoring-rozwoju-obszarow-wiejskich>

⁷ <https://wzs.wzp.pl/programowanie-rozwoju/ereqion-nowoczesne-obszernatorium-rozwoju-wojewodztwa>

⁸ <https://polskawliczbach.pl>

⁹ <https://analizy.minitorozwoju.pl>

3. Country overview: Poland

3.1 Territorial system of Poland

Poland is currently (as of 01/01/2024) divided into **16 voivodeships**, which are the highest level of regional administration. Each voivodeship is administered by a regional government. In addition, voivodeships are divided into **314 poviats (counties)**, and these in turn into **2,477 gminas (communes)** (302 urban, 711 urban-rural and 1,464 rural ones), which are the smallest administrative units. There are also **66 cities with county rights**. Municipalities have supportive units; these are villages and they include a number of villages. There are **40,836 villages** in Poland (Statistics Poland) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Map of Poland

Source: https://pl.wikipedia.org/wiki/Podzia%C5%82_administracyjny_Polski

There is also a special category of cities – cities with county rights, which are both local government units and administrative subdivisions at the poviats level. These cities have their own city councils and executive authorities, replacing the functions of both counties and communes.

There are also other administrative units in Poland, such as **regions, macro-regions or functional areas**. The number of these units can be defined according to various criteria, and there is neither a nationwide classification combining all these typologies nor their ranking. Regions may be defined on the basis of various criteria, such as geography, economy, culture or infrastructure. They can be, for example, tourist regions, industrial regions, agricultural regions, historical regions, etc. The size of

regions and lower administrative units as well as the average number of their residents differ widely. There is a trend of depopulating rural and urban communities in peripheral areas characterised by lower than the average GDP per capita. Poland is mostly a plain country with mountains in the southern border regions at the Polish-Czech and Polish-Slovakian borders.

3.2 Strategies and policies

In Poland, there are several policies, instruments and initiatives at national level that aim to support the **sustainable development of rural areas**, improve the quality of life of rural people and stimulate the local economy and entrepreneurship:

1. **Rural Development Program (RDP)** that ended last year and was financed by the European Union and national funds, which aimed to support the sustainable development of rural areas. RDP included a number of activities supporting agriculture, development of rural entrepreneurship, protection of the natural environment and improvement of the quality of life in the countryside.
2. **Community-led local development strategies** (Local Action Groups – LAGs). LAGs are non-profit organizations that operate at the local level and involve residents and local institutions in the decision-making process regarding rural development. Support for LAGs is provided, among others, by Rural Development Programs and currently national CAP strategic plans.
3. **EU national recovery and resilience plan**. Poland created national recovery and resilience plan as part of the EU response to the COVID-19. These national resilience and recovery plans may include investments in infrastructure, support for the local community and other actions aimed at restoring normality and supporting development in crisis-affected areas.

Yet, these policies are limited in scope and resources and their impact is decreasing with each of the programming period due to the fact that vast majority of resources is devoted to direct payments. Moreover, the measures targeted at local authorities require their contribution and the communes most in need of investment generally do not have resources to apply for support. There are also no Polish state policies and instruments to accompany the EU support.

In Poland, there are several policies, instruments and initiatives at national level that aim to support **social exclusion** in rural areas:

1. **Socio-economic development programs**. Implemented under the Rural Development Program (RDP), they may include initiatives supporting the development of rural communities, including educational, cultural, recreational projects and the promotion of social activity.
2. **Aid funds for non-governmental organizations**. The state may provide financial support to non-governmental organizations operating in rural areas that undertake activities aimed at social exclusion. Such organizations may conduct integration projects, training, workshops, or programs activating local communities.

3. **Professional activation programs.** These offer vocational training, courses, internships and support for entrepreneurship in rural areas, which aims to increase employment opportunities and develop competences of rural residents. These programs are funded from the Labour Fund to which each employer has to contribute and can make use of the support offered within these programs (this support is based on the Act of 20 April 2004 on employment promotion and labour market institutions, OJ of 2024, pos. 475, 742, 858, 863, 1089, 1572). Also unemployed people can make use of this support through potential employers or by support to undertaking economic activity.
4. **Integration and cultural initiatives.** The state can support various cultural, artistic and integration initiatives, such as festivals, meetings, workshops and exhibitions that promote social activity and strengthen social ties in rural areas.
5. **Support programs for older and disabled people.** There are financial programs and social initiatives that aim to improve the quality of life of elderly and disabled people living in rural areas. These may include, for example, health care, transport or social activation services. Within the State Rehabilitation Fund for Disabled there are offered also loans for disabled people for undertaking non-agricultural economic activity.
6. **Rural revitalization projects.** As part of these projects, actions are taken to improve social and municipal infrastructure in rural areas, which may contribute to increasing the attractiveness of life and social activity of residents.

The purpose of the above-mentioned policies, instruments and initiatives is to improve the quality of life, strengthen communities, build social bonds, integrate various social groups, promote social and cultural activity, increase opportunities on the labour market, professional activation, support local entrepreneurship, create jobs, reduce social and educational barriers, as well as economic and cultural ones. The main tasks of the above-mentioned policies, instruments and initiatives are the creation of support programs, promoting social activity, development of social infrastructure, support for social entrepreneurship, education and training, promoting dialogue and social participation but not the creation of new enterprises or economic activity apart from the professional activation programs or State Rehabilitation Fund for Disabled. Cooperation between public institutions, private businesses and social economy entities is crucial for the effective implementation of policies and initiatives supporting social exclusion in rural areas. Cooperation between public institutions, private businesses and social economy entities is crucial for the effective implementation of policies and initiatives supporting social exclusion in rural areas. These activities require coordination, social involvement and appropriate allocation of financial and human resources.

A good example of the above-mentioned policies is currently implemented measure “NGO support for accessibility and social inclusion” within the EU social funds. This measure offers support for:

- a) “counselling on strengthening the capacity of NGOs to provide services in the field of social inclusion and ensuring accessibility for persons with special needs;

- b) enhancement of the expert competences of NGO representatives as necessary to provide services in the area of social inclusion and accessibility to persons with special needs;
- c) reviewing processes and implementing improvements in NGOs' activities in the field of accessibility and social inclusion.”¹⁰

In 2011 Poland reached its highest population number with 38,538,000 residents, while in 2022 there were only 37,766,000 residents (Statistics Poland, 2023, p. 26). They are concentrated in the most developed cities and neighbouring them communes. The main cities include: Warsaw – central Poland, Śląskie conurbation – south Poland, Tri-city – north Poland, Wrocław – south-western Poland, Poznań – central-western Poland and Szczecin – north-western Poland.

The average population density in Poland is 121 persons per km². However, there are significant regional and intraregional differences. The lowest population density characterises Opolskie region (bordering with the Czech Republic) – 16 persons per km², while the highest population density is observed in Opolskie's eastern neighbour – Śląskie region where it reaches 153 persons per km² (Statistics Poland, 2023, pp. 66-69).

There is general depopulation and ageing trend in Poland. However, there are significant regional and intraregional differences. Generally, eastern Poland is depopulating and aging faster than western part. Remote rural areas are depopulating and aging faster than rural areas close to big cities. Small cities are depopulating and aging faster than bigger ones (Główny Urząd Statystyczny, 2022).

Until 2022 Russian invasion to Ukraine the number of permanent immigrants was insignificant. Over 1 million of Ukrainian worked in Poland but they mostly used temporary permits meaning that after several months in Poland they had to come back to Ukraine and apply for a next work permit. After February 2022, there was a huge influx of Ukrainians. They concentrated in big cities. Before the war, big farms, especially, producing fruit and vegetables hired season workers from Ukraine which after the war broke became more difficult.

Currently, in big cities more and more Asian immigrants can be observed due to shortages of labour force in services, construction and certain professions (ex. Welder). The immigrants are generally not integrated in Polish social fabric. Some level of integration is easier for Ukrainians and Belarusians (influx of them after 2020 presidential elections in Belarus) due to similarities of the languages and cultures. For most Asians it is more difficult due to language and cultural barriers.

The major industries in Poland concentrate around natural resources, fuels and energy. Agri-food sector is also important when it comes to the Polish foreign trade balance. The most important trade partners for Poland are the EU member states, especially Germany.

The current key economic challenge is the so-called middle-income trap. During the 20 years of the Polish EU membership, Polish export was based on the price competitiveness that resulted from lower labour costs. Increases in labour costs and costs of energy make the Polish products less competitive.

¹⁰ Source: <https://www.funduszeuropejskie.gov.pl/nabory/47-wsparcie-ngo-w-zakresie-dostepnosci-i-wlaczania-spolecznego/>

Poland is looking for ways to prevent falling into middle income trap but so far with no success due to lack of consistent state policy supporting the transformation of the Polish economy.

Aging and low natural increase of the population are the key problems and barriers for socio-economic development. They also pose a serious burden on social security system and healthcare. The attempt to increase the retirement age failed and there is still no acceptance to increase it although it is not high in comparison with other countries. Currently, women can retire at the age of 60 while men at the age of 65.

In recent years inequalities in income distribution decreased in Poland due to significant increase in minimum salary and introduction in 2016 of a payment for children. This also led to a decrease in the poverty rate. However, the significant inflation rate after the COVID-19 pandemic stopped the decrease in poverty rate and a growing number of households struggles with food and energy costs (Bień, 2022).

3.3 Territorial inequalities in Poland

There are regions in Poland that are characterized by an unfavourable socio-economic situation. There are many factors that influence which regions are considered disadvantaged, including economic, social, infrastructural and demographic indicators. Some rural areas may struggle with problems such as poverty, unemployment, lack of infrastructure, or limited access to public services. We can distinguish several types of areas with unfavourable socio-economic situation (Stanny 2013):

- **Areas that used to be heavily dependent on industry** but have lost importance as a result of economic restructuring. Such regions may have a high unemployment rate and no development prospects.
- **Cross-border areas** may be considered disadvantaged due to difficulties arising from the specific nature of border regions, such as geographical isolation, poor infrastructure or limited opportunities for economic development.
- **Regions with demographic problems:** areas with an aging population, emigration of young people and limited fertility may face difficulties in maintaining socio-economic stability.
- **Areas with high levels of unemployment and low levels of education** that may find it difficult to ensure sustainable socio-economic development.
- **Post-state farm villages,** these are located mainly in northern part of Poland. The residents of these villages used to work in the state farms before 1990s and during the socio-economic transformation when these farms were shut down, they had problems in finding new jobs. The problem has been “inherited” by the next generations. This is also a result from the fact that these farms were located mainly in peripheral areas with no industry and other potential jobs.

Support for these areas may be implemented through development programmes, infrastructure investments, support for entrepreneurship, education and other activities aimed at stimulating development and improving the quality of life for residents.

There are several main unfavourable territorial conditions in Poland that may affect the socio-economic development of various areas of the country:

- Some areas of Poland are characterized by **poverty of natural resources**, such as fertile soils. The lack of these resources may hinder the development of agriculture, industry and tourism.
- Some regions of Poland, especially those located in the north and east of the country, may experience difficult **climatic conditions**, such as long winters, low temperatures, or frequent rain or snowfall. These conditions may affect agriculture, infrastructure and the quality of life of residents.
- In some areas of Poland, **transport, energy and telecommunications infrastructure** may be insufficient or underdeveloped. Difficulties in access to the road and rail transport network or lack of access to broadband Internet may hinder economic development and interregional communication.
- Some regions of Poland are struggling with problems related to **population aging, low fertility and emigration of young people**. This may lead to a decreasing population, a limited labour market and an increase in the burden on social and health care systems.
- Areas occasionally exposed to **natural disasters**, such as floods, droughts or other effects of weather extremes.

A good indicator of the situation of rural communes in different Polish regions is their income from PIT and CIT taxes as it shows the level of economic activity of businesses and residents and depends also on the unemployment rate and average business and personal incomes. The figure 1 shows that even within different Polish regions there is a significant diversity of the economic situation of rural communes. From the figure it is visible that the richest communes are the ones neighbouring the largest cities – mainly regional capitals. It is also clear that eastern part of Poland is on average worst off than the western one.

Figure 2. Rural and urban-rural incomes from PIT and CIT taxes per capita

Legend: Amounts in PLN; in brackets – number of rural and urban-rural communes; grey areas – urban communes. Amounts: PLN 850 = app. EUR 210; PLN 700 = app. EUR 175; PLN 550 = app. EUR 137; PLN 400 = app. EUR 100.

Source: Stanny, Rosner and Komorowski, (2023), Fig. IV.50.

3.4 Social economy

The history of social economy in Poland has rich roots dating back to the **19th century**, but its development was often conditioned by political, social and economic changes in the country. The first initiatives related to the social economy in Poland appeared in the 19th century, mainly in the form of **consumer, agricultural and craft cooperatives**. The first consumer cooperative was founded in 1844 in Poznań (Frączak, 2006).

In the **interwar period**, especially after Poland regained independence in 1918, the social economy movement strengthened. Various types of cooperatives, associations and institutions supporting the development of local communities have been established, including: savings and loan associations, worker cooperatives and mutual insurance companies.

During the **Polish People's Republic**, the social economy operated alongside the planned economy, controlled by the State. During this period, various forms of cooperatives developed, such as housing, food and production cooperatives. As the state controlled all types of organisations their activities

were strictly limited and monitored by the state. Only specific types of activities – in line with the policies of the ruling party – were allowed.

After the **political transformation in 1989**, when Poland moved from a centrally planned economy to a market economy, the social economy (NGOs, foundations) played an important role in the process of the country's socio-economic transformation. During this period, many new economic initiatives were created, including social cooperatives, foundations, associations and social enterprises. The rules for creating such initiatives were changed from the ones in force until 1989. This allowed for creation of initiatives dealing with issues not present in social economy before 1989 such as social inclusion, especially support for disabled people.

The **modern social economy** in Poland is developing dynamically. Social economy institutions are economic and social entities operating in all sectors. They can take various forms, including: **cooperative banks, mutual insurance, cooperatives, guarantee funds, social enterprises, associations, foundations** and cover a wide range of activities and initiatives to support local communities, fight against social exclusion, support sustainable development, and create jobs for excluded people. Currently, the social economy in Poland mainly helps prevent social exclusion and alleviates social tensions, supporting the process of building a civil society. It also meets the priorities of the European Union: social cohesion, full employment and the fight against poverty, participatory democracy, better governance and stable development. These entities are particularly active in areas such as: **social protection, social services, health, banking, insurance, agricultural production, retail, associated work, crafts, housing sector, supplies, resident services, training and education, cultural scope, sports and entertainment**. The process of developing social economy is both bottom-up and top-down. The needs of bottom-up local initiatives were acknowledged when developing Polish social policy and special regulations and support programmes were prepared to help such entities and to enable social integration of vulnerable groups.

Public authorities well understand the essence and role of the social economy and take **specific actions to support its development** (*Uchwała nr 212 Rady Ministrów z dnia 26 października 2022 r.*). Social economy entities actively identify with the concept of the social economy and engage in initiatives promoting its development. According to the act of 5th August 2022 on social economy¹¹ social economy entities include:

- social cooperatives,
- occupational therapy workshops and a vocational activity centres,
- social integration centres and a social integration clubs,
- work cooperatives, including a cooperative of invalids and a cooperative of the blind, and a cooperative of agricultural production,

¹¹ https://orka.sejm.gov.pl/proc9.nsf/ustawy/2321_u.htm

- non-governmental organisations, excluding political parties and trade unions.

Social economy organizations can conduct a variety of activities covering a wide range of economic sectors and social areas. Below are examples of typical activities of social economy organizations along with the corresponding NACE codes (classification of economic activities):

1. Manufacturing and retail:

- Retail sales in non-specialized food stores (NACE code: 47.11)
- Retail sales in non-specialized non-food stores (NACE code: 47.19)
- Retail sales in specialized food, beverage and tobacco stores (NACE code: 47.21)
- Retail sales in specialized stores selling other food products (NACE code: 47.29)

2. Social and care services:

- Social care with specialization in the care of the elderly, disabled people and those with chronic diseases (NACE code: 88.10)
- Social assistance with specialization in housing (NACE code: 88.10)
- Social assistance with specialization in social support without accommodation (NACE code: 88.10)
- Auxiliary activities related to health care (NACE code: 88.10)

3. Education:

- Primary school activities (NACE code: 85.20)
- Secondary school activities (NACE code: 85.31)
- Activities of supporting educational institutions (NACE code: 85.60)

4. Social work with marginalized groups:

- Activities of trade union organizations (NACE code: 94.20)
- Activities of organizations of employed persons (NACE code: 94.20)
- Activities of recreational, cultural and sports organizations (NACE code: 94.99)

5. Social farming:

- Growing vegetables, fruits, nuts, roots and legumes (NACE code: 01.13)
- Production of milk and dairy products (NACE code: 10.51)
- Poultry farming (NACE code: 01.47)
- Production of other products not included elsewhere (NACE code: 10.89)

3.5 Social enterprises in Poland

Social enterprises in Poland are considered as part of a sub-division within the Polish social economy system and are among the entities named as part of solidarity economy. These are the entities that focus on social integration and labour activation of people in danger of social exclusion (*Uchwała nr 212 Rady Ministrów z dnia 26 października 2022 r.*). These entities are being developed and supported by the state policy as part of the efforts to integrate the groups in danger of social exclusion.

According to the report of the Department of Social and Solidarity Economy in the Ministry of Family and Social Policy entitled "Information on the operation of social cooperatives operating under the Act of April 27, 2006 on **social cooperatives** for the period 2020-2021":

1. Number of social cooperatives in Poland.
 - The number of social cooperatives has remained relatively stable in recent years. At the end of 2020, there were 1,497 social cooperatives in the National Court Register (not in liquidation and not deleted), i.e. almost $\frac{3}{4}$ of all social cooperatives registered at that time (2,025 entities). At the end of 2021, the number of social cooperatives increased to 1,503 (compared to 2,080 total registered entities).
 - Comparing the number of social cooperatives per 100,000 inhabitants, there is a noticeable difference between individual voivodeships. The voivodeships with the most social cooperatives are: Wilkopolskie (177 in 2020 and 176 in 2021), Śląskie (150 in 2020 and 144 in 2021) and Mazowiecki (153 in 2020 and 157 in 2021). While the fewest cooperatives operated in the Opolskie voivodeship (40 in 2020 and 2021), Świętokrzyskie (42 in 2020 and 40 in 2021) and Podlaskie (57 in 2020 and 56 in 2021).
2. Structure and employment in social cooperatives.
 - In the light of information collected by the institution responsible for social security in Poland, in 2020-2021, a total of approx. 10,000 people were employed in social cooperatives.
 - The vast majority of people employed in social cooperatives worked under an employment contract (over 60%). The second largest group were people performing work on the basis of a temporary contract, which constituted over 30% of the total. The remaining employees worked under other forms of employment.
 - The vast majority of people working in social cooperatives were women. There were more than twice as many of them as men and in the reporting years their share was almost 70% of all workers.
 - People with certified disabilities constituted almost 20% of all people working in social cooperatives, the most numerous in this group were people with moderate disabilities (over 60%).
3. Membership in the audit association.

- The function of the audit association for all non-affiliated cooperatives, including social cooperatives, is performed by the National Cooperative Council, which is also the supreme body of the cooperative self-government. In addition, the National Council keeps a register of all audit associations.
- Currently, there are two audit associations in which social cooperatives can be associated: the National Audit Association of Social Cooperatives and the Regional Cooperative Audit Association in Olsztyn.
- The National Audit Association of Social Cooperatives associated 307 social cooperatives in 2020, while in 2021 the number of social cooperatives associated was 346.
- At the end of 2021, the Regional Cooperative Audit Association in Olsztyn brought together 16 social cooperatives. Almost 60% of social cooperatives located their activities in one of the five dominant sections of the activity list: wholesale and retail trade (17.4%), industrial processing (15.3%), administrative services and support activities (11.4%), construction (8.1 %) and professional, scientific and technical activities (6.5%).

4. The period of operation of social cooperatives.

- Data on the period of operation of social cooperatives indicate that almost 40% of social cooperatives have been active for 7 to 9 years. Another group, constituting almost 30% of all social cooperatives, are relatively "young" entities that have been operating for 2 to 4 years. About 15% of social cooperatives have been operating for more than 10 years. The fact that the entity has remained on the market for such a long time may indicate that these cooperatives have found a market niche in which they pursue their interests and increase their economic potential.

3.5.1 Strategic framework

The strategy on development of social economy (*Uchwała nr 212 Rady Ministrów z dnia 26 października 2022 r.*) set a goal of creating 35 thousand new work places in social enterprises by 2030. In this strategy a number of jobs created in social enterprises co-financed by the EU funds – ESF and ESF+ is estimated (Table 1). A significant increase is expected in most of the Polish regions.

Table 1. Estimated number of jobs created between 2014 and 2030 in social enterprises thanks to ESF and ESF+ support

Region	Number of jobs created by 2023 within the regional operational programmes (RPOs)	Number of jobs to be create in the period 2021-2030	Total for 2014-2030
Dolnośląskie	580	931	1 511
Kujawsko-Pomorskie	601	1 298	1 899
Lubelskie	493	1 558	2 051
Lubuskie	524	648	1 172

Łódzkie	497	1 436	1 933
Małopolskie	625	1 358	1 983
Mazowieckie	614	1 540	2 154
Opolskie	177	672	849
Podkarpackie	459	1 463	1 922
Podlaskie	1 682	872	2 554
Pomorskie	465	994	1 459
Śląskie	1 711	2 080	3 791
Świętokrzyskie	261	973	1 234
Warmińsko-Mazurskie	691	1 080	1 771
Wielkopolskie	1 422	1 143	2 565
Zachodniopomorskie	368	1 155	1 523
Total	11 170	19 201	30 371

Source: Uchwała nr 212 Rady Ministrów z dnia 26 października 2022 r., tab. 2.

There are many **national strategies and legal frameworks** supporting the activities of social economy organizations in Poland. They aim to support and develop the social economy sector in Poland by creating a favourable operating environment and providing financial and institutional support for social economy organizations. Among them there can be listed:

1. **Operational Programmes** related to the EU Social Funds and **regional programmes** that are implemented under European funds and include support for the social economy sector.
2. **Social Policy** – Polish social policy includes a number of activities supporting social economy organizations, including, for example, support programs for people at risk of poverty and social exclusion, social rehabilitation projects, and initiatives promoting professional activity.
3. **Legal provisions** regulating the activities of social economy organizations, such as the Act on public benefit activities and volunteering, or the Act on social cooperatives, which determine the principles of operation of these organizations and access to public support.
4. **Local initiatives**, many local governments take initiatives to support the social economy sector in their area, e.g. by providing subsidies, organizing competitions for social projects or cooperation with local non-governmental organizations.

The social economy can contribute to local development in many different ways:

1. Job creation, social enterprises, cooperatives, and other organizations work to create jobs in local communities. They may employ people who are in a difficult situation on the labour market, such as long-term unemployed people, disabled people, or people excluded from the labour market.

2. Support for micro-enterprises and local initiatives, these organizations support the development of micro-enterprises and local social initiatives by providing loans, training, mentoring and access to a network of contacts and business partners.
3. Providing social services, such as care for the elderly, support for disabled people, help for the homeless, or education and psychological support. Thanks to this, they contribute to improving the quality of life of residents of local communities. Such services are often conducted by NGOs.
4. Social activation and social integration, engaging residents of local communities in local activities, building social bonds, developing skills and strengthening self-esteem and social involvement.
5. Sustainable local development, i.e. development that simultaneously takes into account social, ecological and economic aspects. Through their activities, these organizations can contribute to protecting the natural environment, strengthening local communities and promoting social and economic justice.

The Polish Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Policy is responsible for the development of social policy in Poland (there is a dedicated Department of Social Economy)¹². The social economy is defined as “a sphere in which economic activity serves social objectives. It is primarily concerned with the employment and reintegration of people who are extremely disadvantaged and at risk of social exclusion. These are particularly the disabled, the unemployed and senior citizens. However, better fitting jobs to their needs is not everything. Among the social objectives is also the promotion of the subjectivity and independence of these people, rebuilding their ability to participate more fully in social and working life. These are also activities for local development”¹³.

Social economy entities are obliged to follow the development goals of social and solidarity in Poland. These include:

- “social enterprises (e.g. social cooperatives), which employ at least half of people from groups at risk of social exclusion - the disabled, the unemployed, 30% of people with moderate or severe disabilities;
- reintegration units, i.e. units whose main objective is the social and professional reintegration of people at risk of social exclusion (e.g. Occupational Activity Works, Occupational Therapy Workshops or Social Integration Centres);

¹² The ministry is supported by the National Committee for the Development of the Social Economy which is an opinion-giving and advisory body. The Committee's tasks include, inter alia, presenting opinions on the development programme for social economy, draft legislation and other documents related to the functioning of social economy entities, as well as the functioning of the Act. Developing proposals for measures for the development of social economy of an innovative nature, as well as presenting periodic information on its activity to the minister competent for social security (<https://www.ekonomiaspoleczna.gov.pl/co-robimy/krajowy-komitet-rozwoju-ekonomii-spolecznej/okomitecie/>).

¹³ <https://www.gov.pl/web/rodzina/ekonomia-spoleczna-i-solidarna-1>

- entities operating in the public benefit sphere, such as associations, foundations and entities of the economic cooperatives, the purpose of which is the employment of, for example, invalids and the blind.”

According to the mentioned Ministry there are currently app. 100,000 social economy entities in Poland¹⁴. The Ministry's tasks include the creation of conditions for the development of social and solidarity economy and support for cooperation between public administration and social economy entities.

Social economy entities may benefit from grants and repayable financial instruments – loans and guarantees. Grants are provided by Social Economy Support Centres, which have funds at their disposal from the European Social Fund (under Regional Operational Programmes). These funds are earmarked for creating new jobs in existing or newly created social enterprises. Social economy entities may also benefit - as all business start-ups - from subsidies from the Labour Fund paid by Poviats Labour Offices. It is also possible to obtain subsidies from the State Fund for Rehabilitation of Disabled Persons for the Loans are provided under the National Social Entrepreneurship Fund.

Loans are granted by selected Financial Intermediaries: Towarzystwo Inwestycji Społeczno-Ekonomicznych TISE S.A. and the Walbrzych Region Fund. To date, nearly 400 loans have been granted, benefiting almost 300 social economy entities, for a total amount of app. PLN 45 million (EUR 10 million) (as of September 2018). In addition to grants, support implemented by the Social Economy Support Centres includes non-financial support, i.e. local animation, assistance in creating social enterprises, advisory and training support.

The activities of the Ministry of Labour and Social Policy aimed at supporting the development of the social economy sector also include a number of other activities, such as:

- “trainings for representatives of social enterprises in the field of public procurement,
- training and networking of Social Economy Support Centres,
- counselling for regions on creation of public policies on social economy,
- support for creation of clusters and social franchising systems¹⁵, employment of disabled persons,
- creation of an educational package with content from the field of social economy for teachers and support for the creation of student cooperatives,
- preparation of a programme and delivery of managerial and MBA studies in social enterprise management.”¹⁶

¹⁴<https://www.gov.pl/web/rodzina/ekonomia-spoleczna-i-solidarna-1>

¹⁵ Systems offering operating under an already established name with clear operating procedures that can be implemented in other parts of Poland.

¹⁶ <https://www.gov.pl/web/rodzina/wsparcie-podmiotow-ekonomii-spolecznej>

The National Programme for the Development of the Social Economy was adopted in 2014. The reason for its preparation was an obligation to have such a programme under the 2014-2020 EU financial perspective which included thematic objective 9 'Promoting social inclusion, combating poverty and all discrimination'. In 2019 this programme was changed to include a perspective towards 2030 and the new regulations related to the EU financial perspective 2023-2027. The strategic objective of the National Programme is to make the social economy an important instrument of active social policy, support for social and local development. It is stated that by 2030, social economy entities will be an important element in the activation and social integration of people at risk of social exclusion and providers of social services. To achieve this goal four specific objectives were formulated:

1. Support sustainable partnership of social economy entities with local government in the delivery of social services.
2. Increase the number of quality jobs in social enterprises for persons threatened by social exclusion.
3. Increase the competitiveness of social economy entities on the market.
4. Disseminate positive attitudes towards the social economy (*Uchwała nr 212 Rady Ministrów z dnia 26 października 2022 r.*).

In relation to these four specific objectives there are four activity areas name:

Area I. Solidary local community:

Priority 1: Development of social services:

Measure I.1.1. Development of solutions ensuring increased participation of social economy entities of social economy in implementation of social services.

Measure I.1.2. Development of public-social partnerships.

Measure I.1.3. Development of social services for families, children and youth, persons with disabled, dependants and the elderly household members, people with mental disorders and persons in crisis of homelessness.

Measure I.1.4. Increasing participation of social economy entities in public procurement public

Priority 2: Inclusion of social economy actors in local development procurement:

Measure I.2.1. Development of cooperation network of Social Economy Support Centres – LAGs.

Measure I.2.2. Revitalisation and local development.

Area II. Solidarity labour market:

Priority 1: Supporting social and professional reintegration of persons threatened by social exclusion in reintegration units:

Measure II.1.1. Preparation for professional activation of participants of occupational therapy workshops occupational therapy workshops.

Measure II.1.2. Development of social employment.

Priority 2: Vocational activation of people with disabilities and the elderly in social economy entities elderly in social economy entities:

Measure II.2.1. Support for employment of people with disabilities in the sheltered and open labour market.

Measure II.2.2. Support for activation of disabled youth - in particular graduates of special schools providing vocational education and special schools foster labour.

Measure II.2.3. Creation of conditions for continued economic activity of older people in elderly in social economy entities.

Priority 3: Creating jobs for people at risk of exclusion in social enterprises:

Measure II.3.1. Social enterprise status.

Measure II.3.2. Instruments to support social enterprises.

Area III. Competitive social entrepreneurship:

Priority 1: Increasing the competitiveness of social economy entities:

Measure III.1.1. Increasing access to repayable capital for social economy entities.

Measure III.1.2. Development of tax instruments for social economy entities.

Measure III.1.3: Developing the innovative potential of social economy actors and testing and scaling new solutions.

Priority 2: Support for the development of professionalisation and cooperation of social economy entities and intersectoral cooperation:

Measure III.2.1. Development of social economy support services and inclusion of social economy entities in the support system for micro-, small and medium-sized enterprises.

Measure III.2.2. Development of sectoral networks, co-operatives, consortia - including cooperatives, social franchising.

Measure III.2.3. Preparation and strengthening of human resources for the social economy sector - in especially management staff.

Area IV. Solidarity society:

Priority 1: Shaping positive attitudes towards social economy among youth:

Measure IV.1.1. Developing social and entrepreneurial competences for social economy among youth.

Measure IV.1.2. Developing social and entrepreneurial competences in formal education among youth.

Measure IV.1.3. Preparing personnel to work with youth on developing social and entrepreneurial competences.

Priority 2: Creating social economy brand:

Measure IV.2.1. Popularization of social economy among citizens.

Measure IV.2.2. Popularization of social economy among representatives of public administration.

In the programme it was also decided how to finance social economy within the regional programmes under the EU financial framework 2023-2027. The decision was based on the need to maintain an appropriate level of concentration of available resources to meet specific employment targets. Therefore, at least 60% of the funds envisaged in the regional programmes for support for the social economy sector should be allocated for non-repayable financial support for job creation and reintegration in the social entities. Three instruments are used: a grant for the creation of a workplace, a temporary support for the maintenance of the workplace and measures for the socio-professional reintegration of the employees of a social enterprise whose employment has been subsidised from the above source. This means that the remaining costs, including comprehensive non-financial support services for the social economy sector and animating the development of its potential to provide social services, should not exceed 40% of the allocation available for social economy.

Currently it is possible to apply for support to create workplaces in social economy entities and receive up to app. EUR 8,750 for one workplace. One entity can apply for creation of up to 10 workplaces¹⁷.

3.5.2 Policies/instruments/initiatives – supporting the social economy and/or social enterprises

The most important document regulating the development of social economy in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship is Zachodniopomorskie **Programme for the Development of Social Economy** adopted for implementation by the Board of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship on 4 December 2017. The programme is consistent with **the National Programme for the Development of Social Economy**¹⁸, and higher-level strategies at national and European level. The **National Programme for the Development of Social Economy** is a government program that sets out key public policy directions for the social economy and social enterprises. The main objective of this programme is "By 2030, social economy entities will be an important element of activation and social integration of people at risk of social exclusion and providers of social services". It defines the directions of public intervention aimed at shaping the best possible conditions for the development of social economy and social enterprises in Poland. The National Programme for the Development of Social Economy is a programme for the development of (The Act of 6 December 2006 on the Principles of Conducting Development Policy (OJ of 2021, item 1057, as amended) and is an operational and implementation document, established in order to implement the medium-term strategy for the development of the country – the Strategy for

¹⁷ <https://fundusze.ngo.pl/452929-wsparcie-finansowe-na-tworzenie-nowych-miejsc-pracy.html>

¹⁸ <https://www.gov.pl/web/rodzina/dokumenty-programowe-i-strategiczne> Accessed on 26 August 2024

Responsible Development, as well as other development strategies, in particular the **Social Capital Development Strategy**, the **Human Capital Development Strategy**. The National Programme for the Development of Social Economy was adopted in 2014 in accordance with the Partnership Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Poland and the European Commission on the financial perspective 2014-2020, it is a key operational and implementation document within the scope of Thematic Objective 9 "Promoting social inclusion, combating poverty and any discrimination", which is an ex ante condition for the implementation of activities in Poland in this area. The programme also defines the most important assumptions and framework of the intervention co-financed in the EU financial perspective 2021-2027 in the scope of Thematic Objective 4 "Europe with a stronger social dimension" (area: social inclusion and integration), co-creating together with other strategic and programme documents the framework of the state policy in the field of social inclusion. The results of this program are: 1. An increase in the share of funds from local government budgets allocated to commissioning the provision of social services to social economy entities; 2. Increasing the employment of people at risk of social exclusion in high-quality jobs in social enterprises; 3. Increasing the number of social economy entities conducting business activity or paid public benefit activities; 4. Increasing the membership of young people under 18 years of age in social economy entities. It was assumed that by 2030 local government units will allocate at least 2% of the budget to commissioning the provision of social services to social economy entities, 35 thousand new, high-quality jobs will be created in social enterprises for people at risk of social exclusion, the number of social economy entities conducting business activity or paid public benefit activities will increase by at least 9 thousand, The percentage of people under 18 years of age in the total number of members of associations, similar social organizations, foundations and social religious entities will increase by 5 percentage points, as well as the number of people taking up work after completing participation in reintegration units will increase to 40%. It is estimated that in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship the number of jobs created under the implementation of the programme by 2030 will amount to 927 entities.

In accordance with the **Strategy for Responsible Development**, the role of the social economy has been emphasized in the:¹⁹

- Specific Objective I - Sustainable economic growth based more and more on knowledge, data and organizational excellence. The directions of intervention include: "preparation of legal solutions facilitating their current activities, as well as rewarding these forms of action in the case of the provision of services commissioned by government and local government administration. A mechanism of tax incentives will be prepared for their development and increase in the scale of operations";
- Specific Objective II - Socially sensitive and territorially balanced development. Intervention directions include "improving access to services, including social and health; support for groups at risk of poverty and exclusion and ensuring coherence of social inclusion".

¹⁹<https://www.gov.pl/web/ia/strategia-rozwoju-kapitalu-spolecznego-2030-srks> Accessed on 26 August 2024

The Social Capital Development Strategy and its objectives are in line with the concept of inclusive development and the model of intelligent development. The objectives set out in the strategy are in line with the Sustainable Development Goals set out in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, in particular in the:

- Goal 8: Promote stable, sustainable and inclusive economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.
- Goal 9: Build resilient infrastructure, promote sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.
- Goal 11: To make cities and human settlements safe, stable, sustainable and inclusive (Resolution No. 155 of the Council of Ministers of October 27, 2020 on the adoption of the "Strategy for the Development of Social Capital (cooperation, culture, creativity) 2030").

The main objective of the **Human Capital Development Strategy** is to increase human capital and social cohesion in Poland. The Human Capital Development Strategy also sets four specific objectives²⁰:

1. Improving the level of competences and qualifications of citizens, including digital.
2. Improving citizens' health and the efficiency of the healthcare system.
3. Increasing and improving the use of human capital potential in the labour market.
4. Reducing poverty and social exclusion and improving access to services provided in response to demographic challenges.

These strategies are crucial for the social economy for several reasons. **The Strategy for Responsible Development** puts emphasis on sustainable development, which takes into account social, economic and environmental aspects. This makes it possible to create conditions conducive to the growth of residents' incomes and to increase social and territorial cohesion. **The Social Capital Development Strategy** focuses on building trust, cooperation and social commitment. Strong social capital is the foundation for the effective functioning of the social economy, as it supports cooperation between different actors and increases the effectiveness of social activities. **The Human Capital Development Strategy** aims to improve the qualifications and competences of citizens. Investing in human capital is crucial for the social economy, as a skilled and committed workforce contributes to the innovation and competitiveness of the economy. All of these strategies support social inclusion, which means that different groups in society, including those most at risk of exclusion, have access to resources and opportunities for development. This, in turn, contributes to building a fairer and more sustainable society.

²⁰<https://www.gov.pl/web/rodzina/strategia-rozwoju-kapitalu-ludzkiego-2031> Accessed on 26 August 2024

Zachodniopomorskie Programme for the Development of Social Economy is also in line with the development objectives of the current **Development Strategy of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship**²¹. This strategy identifies priority areas for which strategic objectives of the development policy of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship have been formulated, setting the path to achieving the intended vision of the region's development in the perspective of 2030. It assumes activities in the field of 4 strategic objectives:

1. An open community. Conscious residents and community involvement – open and prepared for the challenges of the future.
2. A dynamic economy. Shaping the high quality of life of residents and strengthening the competitiveness of the region.
3. Efficient local government. Effective self-government – an integrated region. Territorial equality in access to quality public services.
4. Partner region. Strong position and active role in interregional and cross-border relations.

Zachodniopomorskie Programme for the Development of Social Economy in particular contributes to the development of the region's identity and social cohesion, including in particular counteracting poverty and social marginalisation processes. The programme is also consistent with the provisions of the Sectoral Policy for Capital and Social Cohesion in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship for the years 2016-2026²². The document indicates, among other things, the implementation of activities aimed at:

- inspiring all entities and environments to conduct a conscious, effective policy for the family, which in turn will contribute to: reducing the scale of unfavourable phenomena concerning the family, breaking negative patterns passed on to subsequent generations, increasing the potential of the family and the local environment, appreciating the family as the basic subject of the local economy, strengthening and developing civil society, including building social bonds and local identity;
- paying attention to groups of particular social importance: young people and the elderly, which in turn will contribute to: young people's readiness to manage the region of the future, the use of competences of the future by young people, slowing down unfavourable demographic trends, the development of the silver economy area (policy, services, mentoring, brand), reducing public costs related to the aging of the population;
- creating conditions enabling the recovery of dormant capital, which in turn will contribute to: reducing the scale and costs of addictions (with particular emphasis on young people), restoring independence and activity of socially, territorially, normatively and economically excluded people (including people with disabilities, long-term social assistance clients, pockets of poverty and others), reducing financial outlays in the area of social assistance.

²¹ See more: <https://bjp.rbjp.wzp.pl/sites/bjp.wzp.pl/files/articles/srwz2030size0.pdf> Accessed on 26 August 2024

²² http://eregion.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/polityka_na_rzecz_kapitalu_oraz_spoinosci_spolecznej.pdf Accessed on 26 August 2024

Among the institutions supporting the social economy in the region, the following are mentioned: the Regional Centre for Social Policy, Social Economy Support Centres, Labour market institutions (Regional Labour Office in Szczecin, Poviát Labour Offices).

The basic tasks of the Social Policy Centre of the Marshal's Office of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship are to create and promote innovative solutions in the field of social assistance, financial and substantive support for organisations, development and updating of programmes aimed at counteracting social exclusion, development of regional social assistance programmes. In 2022, the Centre organised a conference "Social Economy for the Young". The event was addressed to young people and those interested in spreading the spirit of social economy among the young generation, as well as the development of civic activity, entrepreneurship, social solidarity, volunteering and social competences.

Zachodniopomorskie Committee for the Development of Social Economy is a consultative and advisory, educational and disseminating, consultative and expert institution that cooperates with the Board of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship in activities for the development of social economy. The Committee's tasks include, among others: supporting and promoting the social economy in areas related to the labour market, social integration, development of entrepreneurship and innovation, development of public services and other priorities in which the regional development of the social economy is possible; inspiring and promoting new methods of action in the field of activation, integration and social and professional reintegration of individuals and families at risk of social exclusion; developing and proposing new solutions in the field of implementing social economy (ES WZP. *Scope of the Regulations 2020*²³).

Social Economy Support Centres are non-governmental organisations working to support social economy entities. There are 6 such entities in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship. They form the Network of Zachodniopomorskie Social Economy Support Centres (Report on the state of social economy in Zachodniopomorskie in 2020²⁴). The mission of the Network is to promote the idea of social economy and strengthen the potential of local social economy entities. The main objective of the implemented projects is to prepare local communities and social economy entities for social and/or professional reintegration of m.in. people at risk of social exclusion in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship by increasing access to services and assistance in obtaining capital. It also provides support in the field of granting subsidies for the creation of a job in a social enterprise, conducts local animations, consulting, training, business services.

Social economy entities are also supported by special tools and grants. One of such programs is the "Social Bonus", which supports the development of the local social services market. This program allows local governments to outsource services to social economy entities by offering grants from 25% to 70% of the value of the ordered services. In Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship, as part of the "Social Bonus" programme, the Social Activist Programme was implemented, under which more than 3.7

²³ https://es.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/regulamin_zkres_2020.pdf Accessed on 10 July 2024

²⁴ https://es.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/raport_o_stanie_es_w_województwie_zachodniopomorskim_w_2020_r.pdf Accessed on 10 July 2024

thousand initiatives aimed at improving the quality of life in Zachodniopomorskie have been financed since 2017. In the Gryfice powiat, 14 initiatives were implemented as part of the Social Activist Programme (e.g. "Locally is cool" – a project implemented by the Z Pomysłem [With an Idea] Association, the aim of the project was to promote local economic activities; "Passport to Integration" – a project implemented by the Gryfice powiat and partners, the aim of the project is to counteract the digital exclusion of the county's residents. In addition, under the European Social Development Fund, funds are available for the implementation of social projects that can be used by social economy entities. Applications for grants may be submitted by local government units (e.g. communes or powiats) that decide to outsource the implementation of social services to social economy entities.

In the region of Zachodniopomorskie there are social economy entities, such as: the Social Integration Club, the Social Integration Centre, Occupational Therapy Workshops, Vocational Activity Centres, Social Enterprises, Social Cooperatives as well as Foundations and Associations.

In 2021, there were 63 entities conducting active reintegration activities in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship, including: 12 Social Integration Centres, 22 Social Integration Clubs, 29 Occupational Therapy Workshops, 9 Vocational Activity Centres (Fig. 3). These entities serve the social and professional reintegration of people at risk of social exclusion. They do not have the status of social enterprises, but they can prepare for work in a social enterprise or to run such an enterprise (e.g. a social cooperative). Reintegration activities can be carried out as a service to the local community by social enterprises (Report on the state of social economy in the Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship in 2020²⁵).

Figure 3. Availability of services of reintegration entities in the Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship in 2020

²⁵ https://es.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/raport_o_stanie_es_w_województwie_zachodniopomorskim_w_2020_r.pdf Accessed on 26 August 2024

*Explanation: red - Vocational Activity Centres; green - Occupational Therapy Workshops; yellow - Social Integration Centres; orange - Social Integration Clubs

Source: Report on the state of social economy in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship in 2020²⁶.

An important element of the **social economy is social entrepreneurship**. In 2020, there were **47** such entities in the region. These entities conduct business activity or paid public benefit activities, are tasked with the professional and social activation of people at risk of social exclusion or the provision of social services, and do not privatise profit or balance sheet surplus and are managed in a participatory manner. In addition, in 2020, there were **81 Social Cooperatives, 1,052 Foundations and 3,335 Associations** in Zachodniopomorskie (Report on the state of social economy in Zachodniopomorskie in 2020).

In the Gryfice county there are a total of **125 social economy entities (Occupational Therapy Workshop 3, Social Integration Center 1, Social Cooperative 1, Foundations 17, Associations 103)**. An important element supporting the sphere of social economy is also the informal and grassroots activity of the community, which works for changes in the immediate environment. As a result, informal activity is the base of the social economy, from which both ideas for activities and people involved in the life of local communities who have competences facilitating activity in the social economy sector can penetrate. Informal activity remains difficult to capture from a scientific, administrative and statistical perspective (The Act of 6 December 2006 on the Principles of Conducting Development Policy (OJ of 2021, item 1057, as amended)) (Table 1).

Table 1. Number of social economy entities in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship, by entity type in 2020

Specification	Occupational Therapy Workshop	Vocational Activity Centres	Social Integration Centres	Social Integration Clubs	Social Enterprise	Social Cooperative	Foundations	Association
Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship	29	9	12	13	47	81	1,052	3,335
Gryfice powiat	3	-	1	-	-	1	17	103

Source: Report on the state of social economy in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship in 2020 https://es.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/raport_o_stanie_es_w_województwie_zachodniopomorskim_w_2020_r.pdf Accessed on 26 August 2024

Occupational Therapy Workshop (OTW): operate on the basis of the Act on Vocational and Social Rehabilitation and Employment of Persons with Disabilities. Participants of the Workshops can be people with a disability certificate. The OTW's mission is to develop every day and professional skills and prepare for life in a social environment. The OTW in Zachodniopomorskie is run mainly by associations (24), 5 OTWs are run by the local government and its units.

Vocational Activity Centers (VAC): operate on the basis of the Act on Vocational and Social Rehabilitation and Employment of Persons with Disabilities. VACs can be organized by different

²⁶ https://es.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/raport_o_stanie_es_w_województwie_zachodniopomorskim_w_2020_r.pdf Accessed on 26 August 2024

entities, which means they do not have one specific legal form. VACs are created by municipalities, poviats, foundations, associations or other social organizations whose statutory task is the vocational and social rehabilitation of people with disabilities. The main objective of VAC is to create jobs for people with disabilities who have been diagnosed with autism, mental retardation or mental illness.

Social Integration Centers (SIC): entities that offer education in the field of life planning, learning how to manage money and services of developing vocational and social skills. The activities of SIC are mainly focused on preparing people for work in the service sector. SICs can be run by: foundations, associations, local government units or other entities whose activities are regulated by the Act on Public Benefit Activities and Volunteering. The basis of the SIC's activity is the Social Employment Act.

Social Integration Clubs: They are created by the commune or non-governmental organizations. In Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship, 4 Clubs are run by NGOs (foundations) and 9 by social welfare centres operating in the commune. The Club's activity is regulated by the Act on Social Employment. Social Integration Clubs provide assistance to the unemployed in obtaining employment, socially useful work, public works, legal counselling, assistance in employment, social and housing matters, professional internships. In 2020, the largest group of Club participants were the long-term unemployed, people with disabilities and alcohol addicts.

Social Enterprise (SE): entities that combine economic activity with social goals. A social enterprise is a separate entity in terms of organization and accounting. It can run a business, paid public benefit activity or cultural activity. The main objective of the activity is the social and professional integration of people at risk of social exclusion.

Social Cooperative (SC): operate on the basis of the Act on Social Cooperatives. A social cooperative is a legal form of a social enterprise, which means that it combines economic activity with social goals. A social cooperative is a joint enterprise that is based on the work of the cooperative members. The main objective of the activity is the social and professional reintegration of its members. SCs are an important element of employing people who have difficulties in functioning on the open labour market.

Social economy entities can participate in the certification of their products and services with the "Pro-Social Purchase" mark. The possession of the Social Economy Promotional Mark "**Pro-Social Purchase**" distinguishes social economy entities operating in Zachodniopomorskie. The award of the mark is the result of care for the constant strengthening of the rank and image of social economy entities providing services and producing products of the highest quality, made with exceptional care for the use of social potential. Such a mark can be obtained by entities operating as: social integration centres, vocational activity establishments, social cooperatives, cooperatives for the disabled and the blind, commercial law companies (non-profit company), foundations, associations, other entities that meet the definition of a non-governmental organisation as well as legal persons and organisational units operating on the

basis of the provisions on the relationship between the State and the Catholic Church in Poland (Rules for awarding the ES promotional mark²⁷).

A number of initiatives supporting social economy are organized in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship, including: **Social Economy Fair**, the aim of which is to promote social economy entities operating in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship, as well as to promote the idea of social economy, share experiences and good practices in the field of social economy, build a network of cooperation for the benefit of social economy and the possibility of establishing cooperation by various entities. In addition, the fair aims to support social companies through the opportunity to buy: local products, ceramics, sweet pastries. The fair is a space for the promotion of products and services created by people with disabilities or recovering from the homelessness crisis. On the one hand, they show what the professional activation of employees of social entities looks like, on the other hand, they draw attention to the development of consumer awareness of local companies.

The voivodeship also implemented the project "**Social economy as a key to success**" co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship for 2014-2020, as part of Measure 7.5 Coordination of the development of the social economy sector and support for the development of a network of cooperation of social economy partnerships. The aim of the project is to increase the share of social economy entities in Zachodniopomorskie labour market, including the market of public utility services, by increasing the effectiveness of PES and social economy institutions. Project value: EUR 544,838.36, contribution of European Funds: EUR 463,112.61. Duration: January 1, 2020 – August 31, 2023. The project aimed at improving the coordination of activities for the development of social economy in Zachodniopomorskie by ensuring the functioning of Zachodniopomorskie Committee for the Development of Social Economy together with working groups; and increasing the efficiency of social economy entities and their recognition as suppliers of products and services through the organization of social economy fairs, regional information campaign, via the website.

In the Gryfice powiat, the implementation of the socio-economic development policy and the local development programming policy of the counties is based on the Development Strategy of the Gryfice powiat. In addition, in 2017, the Powiat Strategy for Solving Social Problems in the Gryfice powiat for 2017-2025 was adopted²⁸. Its aim is to rationalize local social policy taking into account the needs of individual social groups. The document is the basis for the implementation of relatively permanent models of social interventions to improve of the living conditions of residents, in particular those who are at risk of marginalization and social exclusion, in order to consequently lead to social integration. Another important document is the County Program for Counteracting Domestic Violence and Protection of Victims of Domestic Violence for the Gryfice County for 2018-2022. The main objective of the programme is to increase the effectiveness of counteracting domestic violence and reduce the scale of this problem in the county by building an integrated and professional support system for

²⁷ https://es.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/zasady_przyznawania_znaku_promocyjnego_es.pdf Accessed on 26 August 2024

²⁸ See more: http://pcpr.gryfice.ibip.pl/public/get_file.php?id=273738 Accessed on 10 July 2024

families at risk of violence, protecting victims of violence, undertaking intervention activities against people using domestic violence, helping perpetrators of violence, combining and coordinating the activities of local services, raising awareness and social sensitivity to the problem domestic violence and its consequences. Another important document supporting social policy in the county is the "**County Action Program for the Disabled in the Gryfice County for 2016-2024**"²⁹. The Programme implementers are organisational units of the poviats and municipalities, including educational institutions, as well as organisations and associations working for the benefit of people with disabilities. The basic and overarching objective of the activities carried out under the Programme is to strive to improve the situation and quality of life of people with disabilities by improving the support system, taking into account educational, social, rehabilitation and treatment activities, and counteracting marginalisation and social exclusion of people with disabilities.

In addition, each of the communes located within the borders of the Gryfice County has a development strategy and a strategy for solving social problems. The areas of the Strategy for Solving Social Problems (Gryfice Commune. Social revitalization in the Gryfice Commune³⁰) refer to:

- counteracting social exclusion caused by unemployment, poverty, homelessness and addictions,
- support for families,
- support the development of children and young people,
- support activities aimed at improving the quality of life of older people and people with disabilities and keeping them in the living environment,
- development of civil society and professionalisation of social services.

²⁹ See more: http://pcpr.gryfice.ibip.pl/public/aet_file.php?id=283305 Accessed on 10 July 2024

³⁰ <https://gryfice.eu/323-rewitalizacja-spooleczna-w-gminie-gryfice.html> Accessed on 10 July 2024

4. Regional overview: Gryfice region

4.1 Geographic and historical aspects

The **Zachodniopomorskie** MAP covers the area of the **Gryfice powiat**. The county is located in north-western Poland, in the **Zachodniopomorskie** Voivodeship (NUTS 2). Since 1 January 1999, Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship has been one of the sixteen voivodeship units of the administrative division of the country. It is located in the north-western part of Polish and covers 114 municipalities and 21 poviats (Fig. 4). It is the fifth largest region of Poland (the area of the voivodeship is 22.9 thousand km²) and the eleventh in terms of the number of inhabitants. In the west, the area of the province borders with Germany (with the federal states of Mecklenburg-Vorpommern and Brandenburg). The northern border of the voivodeship is the Baltic coastline. From the south, the voivodeship borders with the Lubuskie and Wielkopolskie voivodeships, and from the east with the Pomeranian voivodeship. The capital of the voivodeship is the city of Szczecin.

Figure 4. Location of the region in Poland

Source: Diagnostic Report – Portrait of the Gryfice County Partnership Instrument Diagnostic Report³¹

In 2022, there were 3,081 settlements in Zachodniopomorskie, including 66 towns, 1,735 villages and 1,280 settlements, colonies and hamlets concentrated in 1,742 villages (Report on the state of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship for 2023³²). Seven cities of the voivodeship were included in the ministerial list of 139 medium-sized cities losing their socio-economic functions. The Gryfice powiat where the MAP operates covers an area of 1021 km², which is 4.44% of the area of this voivodeship and 0.33% of the area of Polish. 61% of the powiat area is occupied by agricultural land, 28% by forests and forest land, and significant areas of surface water. The town of Gryfice serves as a local administrative, financial, educational and health care centre. The county consists of 6 communes (Fig. 5):

³¹ https://cwg.info.pl/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/ZACH_KAM_raport_diagnostyczny_2022.10.31.pdf Accessed on 27 August 2024

³² https://baw2.wzp.pl/UMWZP/document/7772/Uchwala-862_24 Accessed on 27 August 2024

- three urban-rural communes (Gryfice, Płoty, Trzebiatów),
- three rural communes (Brojce, Karnice, Rewal).

Two communes: Rewal and Trzebiatów, due to their seaside location, are classified as tourist communes. Other communes: Gryfice, Brojce, Karnice, Płoty – are typically agricultural areas, once dominated by state farms. Most of the powiat's communes are largely burdened with social and economic problems due to the large area of the so-called post-state farm areas.

Figure 5. Communes of the Gryfice powiat - MAP area of operation

Source: Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship. (n.a.d.). Powiat: Gryfice. <http://eregion.wzp.pl/powiaty/gryficki> (Accessed on 27 August 2024).

Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship is part of Western Pomerania, and the history of the Gryfice County is inextricably linked to its history. Two pillars played a key role in the history of Western Pomerania in the first post-war years. The first was the maritime economy. The second pillar was agriculture based on state farms. Western Pomerania is one of the regions with the highest nationalization of agricultural economy in Poland, which was largely due to the German heritage. After the war, the existing population was gradually displaced to Germany, and as part of the repatriation action, the inhabitants of the former borderlands of the Second Polish Republic were resettled to these areas, and as part of the Vistula operation – the Ukrainian population from the Subcarpathian and Chełm regions. In the first postwar years, the settlers encountered vast estates belonging to landowners, junkers, and nobles in these areas. These farms, which encompassed more than 100 hectares, featured concentrated facilities such as: farm buildings, housing for labourers and expansive estates belonging to the proprietors (Kraśnicki, 2020). Large post-farm complexes were nationalized, and State Agricultural Farms were established. Some estates were divided among individual farmers, including military settlers (Augustyn-Lendzion, 2010). At the end of the 1960s, the operating costs of state farms were 2-3 times higher than planned. Theft, waste, low wages, lack of staff education, low standard of housing for employees were common (Kraśnicki, 2020). After 1989, the market verified unprofitable state farms. By an administrative decision in 1991, they were liquidated, and the entire state agricultural economy became part of the resources of the Agricultural Property Agency of the State

Treasury and then was incorporated into the structure of the Agricultural Property Agency. The liquidation of state farms resulted in an economic and social catastrophe.

The **cultural landscape** of the Gryfice powiat is a material legacy of the rich history of the region, the result of the clash of Pomeranian, Western European, Polish and Scandinavian influences. The complicated history of the Recovered Territories, where the Gryfice powiat is located, and the total exchange of population after 1945, deprived the region of cultural continuity. As part of the settlement action, newcomers appeared mainly from the Eastern Borderlands and central Polish. The new inhabitants had difficulty growing into the foreign landscape, they did not assimilate the foreign cultural heritage. Polonization, supported by the state's propaganda policy, meant the destruction of all manifestations of the region's past heritage, including the removal of historical place and geographical names if they did not have a Slavic origin. Local traditions have been lost, customs and traditions brought from the home places of the new inhabitants have appeared. As a result of the mixing of customs brought from different regions of the Second Polish Republic, none of which managed to dominate the others, a cultural conglomerate was created, which is becoming more and more stable over time (Augustyn-Lendzion, 2010).

4.2 Demography

According to data for 2022, 56,961 people lived in the Gryfice powiat. The county is sparsely populated (56 people/km²). For comparison, the average for the voivodeship is 72 people per km², and for Poland - 123 people per km². Zachodniopomorskie has the lowest population density index in the country. Since 2012, there has been a steady decrease in the population of the powiat (in 2022 compared to 2012, the number of inhabitants decreased by 7.82%) (GUS, 2023). Similar trends are observed throughout the region.

The urbanization rate (percentage share of urban residents in the total population) in Zachodniopomorskie is 68.5%, while in the Gryfice powiat it is slightly lower than the average for the province and in Poland and amounts to 50.30%. The share of women in the population of residents is 50.57%. The feminization coefficient (the number of women per 100 men) is 102, which is lower than the average for the voivodeship and for Polish³³.

The average age of the inhabitants is 42.2 years and is comparable to the average age of the inhabitants of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship and to the average age of the inhabitants of Poland. The median age of women was 43.4 years and the median age of men was 40.9 years. For comparison, the average age of the EU population is 44.5 years.

People of pre-working age (up to 18 years old) constitute 17.77% of the total population of the Gryfice powiat. The highest percentage of people in the structure of the population are people of working age (58.91%) (men: 18 years - 64 years, women: 18 years - 59 years). Every fourth inhabitant of the county is of post-working age (23.32%). The population aged 14 and over constitutes 14.5% of the total

³³https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki ; <https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/zachodniopomorskie>. Accessed on 5 July 2024

population (women 14.00%; men 14.9%) (voivodship: 14.30%), 67.30% is the population aged 15-64 years (women 65.10%; men 69.50%) (the average for the voivodship is 65.90%), while the population aged 65 and over constitutes 18.30% of the total population of Gryfice powiat (women 20.90%; men 15.60%) (voivodship: 19.80%) (Gryfice Commune. Financial situation of households in 2021³⁴; Report on the state of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship for 2023³⁵). The projected number of inhabitants of the Gryfice powiat will decrease in the coming years.

The ongoing process of population ageing is manifested in particular in the indicators illustrating the **demographic dependency ratio**, which describes how many people of non-working age (pre-working and post-working) there are per 100 people of working age. The dependency ratio is 69.8. Thus, for every 100 people of pre-working and working age, there are almost 70 people of non-working age. An increase in this indicator in the coming years will mean that seniors will be an increasing burden on the economy and working people. On the other hand, **the old-age dependency ratio** (the number of people aged 65 and over per 100 people aged 15-64) is 29.7. The values of these coefficients do not differ significantly from the average for Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship and Polish³⁶.

The county has a negative natural growth rate and a negative migration balance. The natural increase is -396 (for comparison, in 2014 this indicator was -5). In regional terms, the situation in the Gryfice powiat is one of the least favourable in the province. Migration is one of the important processes affecting the demographic situation of a given region, being its most complex component (Drobne, Drešč, 2019). Population flows result from different levels of economic development of a given place. In 2022, 689 registrations in internal traffic and 742 deregistrations were registered in the Gryfice powiat, as a result of which the net of internal migration for the Gryfice powiat is -53.³⁷ Negative net migration significantly reduces the size of the labour force and the reproductive potential of the population. At present, the outflow of population is a problem that strikes with cumulative force for the area of the outflow of inhabitants, as the outflow population consists of young people, potential parents of childbearing age. The outflow of people from a given region thus entails a bundle of socio-economic consequences for the region in question (Józefowicz, 2020).

Table 2. Demographic situation of the region in 2022

Specification	Gryfice powiat	Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship	Poland
Population	56 961	1 640 600	37 698 294
% Women	50.57%	51.46%	49.43%
Increase in natural growth (per 1000 population)	-6,5	-5,3	-3,8
Population density	56 persons/ km ²	75 persons/ km ²	123 persons/km ²
Feminization rate (number of women per 100 men)	102	106	107
Urbanization rate (percentage share of urban residents in the total population)	50.30%	68.5%	60%

³⁴ <http://spow.gryfice.ibip.pl/public/getFile?id=1022348>

³⁵ https://baw2.wzp.pl/UMWZP/document/7772/Uchwala-862_24 Accessed on 5 July 2024

³⁶ https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki#dane-demograficzne. Accessed on 5 July 2024

³⁷ https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki#demografia-w-piqulce. Accessed on 5 July 2024.

People of working age (for men age group 18-64 years, for women - 18-59 years)	58.91%	58.5%	59.2%
Participation in the population of children and adolescents (<14) ³⁸	14.50%	14.30%	15.3%
Share in the population of people 15-65 years old	67.30%	65.90%	65.7%
Participation in the elderly population (65+)	18.30%	19.80%	19%
Internal migration balance	-53	-577	0
Net external (foreign) migration	12	68	1 939
Average age of residents	42,2 years	43,5 years	42,1 years
Demographic dynamics index (ratio of live births to deaths)	0,51	0,39	0,68
Total fertility rate (number of children born to an average woman during the entire reproductive period, 15-49 years)	1,09	1,1	1,26
Dependency ratio	69,8	69,1	69
Old-age dependency ratio	29,7	30,1	29,9

Source: GUS 2023; <https://analizy.monitorrozwoju.pl/> ; <https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/> (Accessed on 5 July 2024).

4.3 Economic situation

Zachodniopomorskie region is agricultural and industrial. The main branches of the voivodeship's economy are the energy, chemical, shipbuilding and wood industries, as well as agri-food production, including the brewing industry and fishing. The four commercial seaports located in the region: Szczecin, Świnoujście, Kołobrzeg and Police, as well as several smaller seaports and fishing harbours, are of great importance for the region.

The specificity of Zachodniopomorskie is a large number of areas of former state agricultural farms (SAF), which are characterized by the accumulation of various social problems. Every fifth village in Zachodniopomorskie is classified as a post-state farm village (Urbanik, 2008). In the region, in connection with the privatization of over 200 state farms, in the years 1992-1993, about 30 thousand people lost their jobs. The unemployment that arose was supposed to be temporary, but unfortunately it turns out to be permanent. The general feature of the community that lives in the areas of former state farms has become passivity and social helplessness. The generally prevailing stagnation and even regression of post-state farm villages led to the alienation and exclusion of the local communities. This exclusion, in addition to the social dimension, is manifested in the economic aspect (financial barrier in access to goods and services), as well as in the spatial aspect (physical distance from large urban centres and the lack or very limited communication by public transport) (Special Inclusion Zone in Zachodniopomorskie³⁹).

Figure 6. Classification of municipalities in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship due to the degree of burden of problematic localities in which state farms operated

³⁸ Polish statistics give 3 age groups: children and adolescents up to 14 years of age, people between 15 and 64 years of age and people 65+. Therefore, we provide data for children up to 14 years of age, not 18, as it was in the template.

³⁹ https://wzs.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/delimitacja_ssw_w_ramach_rpo_wz_01_04_2019.pdf Accessed on 5 July 2024

Source: Special Inclusion Zone in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship

The wealth index (GDP per capita) of Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship in 2021 was EUR 13,595 (the average for Poland was EUR 16,138), which is 84.20% in relation to the national average. The average gross monthly salary in the Gryfice powiat in 2022 was EUR 1,250 (voivodship: EUR 1,427; Poland: EUR 1,632)⁴⁰.

Table 3. Economic situation of the region in 2022 (EUR)

Specification	Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship	Poland
GDP/capita (2021)	13,595	16,138
Disposable income - households (2022)	534	524
Average monthly income per capita in households (2022)	545	1,562
Average gross monthly salary (2022)	1,427	1,632

Source: GUS 2023; <https://analizy.monitorrozwaju.pl>; <https://www.polskawliczbach.pl> Accessed on 5 July 2024.

In 2022, there were 245,268 enterprises registered in Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship (excluding persons running individual farms in agriculture), including 17,409 newly registered entities. Most enterprises are micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (< 250 employees), run by natural persons or operating in the form of a commercial company or a civil partnership. In 2022, there were 8,667 companies registered in the Gryfice powiat (7948 – 2010), including 575 newly registered entities. In 2022, compared to 2010, the number of newly registered entities decreased by 33.37%. The increase in the number of enterprises should be assessed positively, in addition to creating new jobs, they can also encourage residents to open their own enterprises in similar industries. In 2022, 381 business entities were deregistered. It should be considered positive that the number of entities that suspended business activity decreased by 59.43% compared to 2010. This proves good conditions for doing business in the region. In addition, the development of entrepreneurship is one of the conditions necessary to increase the economic potential of the region. Newly registered entities of the creative

⁴⁰https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki#przecietne-miesieczne-wynagrodzenie-brutto Accessed on 5 July 2024

sector (ICT, programming, design (including architecture, publishing, multimedia, advertising, fashion and design), which generate innovative activity with high income were 14. The share of newly registered entities of the creative sector in the total number of newly registered entities was 2.43%⁴¹.

The local market of goods and services is shaped mainly by local companies. 21.88% (1,897) of entities declared that they conducted business activity in the Gryfice powiat in the industry and construction sector. The large share of these companies is a positive phenomenon, because entities involved in production activities employ on average much more people than companies in other sectors. 78.33% (6,789) of entities in the register are classified as other activities. 2.48% (215) of entities declared conducting business activity in the agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing sector. Surprisingly little, considering the fact that the Gryfice county is largely rural, and the communes of Trzebiatów and Rewal (the latter almost along its entire length) are located on the Baltic Sea and have fishing traditions. The favourable location of the Rewal and Trzebiatów communes indicates their tourist character, which seems to affect the entire Gryfice powiat – hence so many companies dealing with other activities, i.e. providing services. Economic activity is concentrated in the private sector, with activities carried out mostly by individuals (79.08%). These are mainly micro-enterprises (0-9 employees). A large share of micro entities in the structure of enterprises indicates a tendency in the perception of the professional sphere, it is an example of the trend of moving away from full-time employment towards self-employment. Starting a business by natural persons allows relatively quick adaptation to the changing realities of the local and regional market, it does not require relatively high expenditure to start a business. Among natural persons conducting business activity, the most frequently declared types of predominant activity are activities related to accommodation and catering services, as well as construction. These statistics are close to the regional average⁴².

The Gryfice powiat, apart from the part located in the coastal belt, is an agricultural county. The average area of a farm in the powiat is about 33 ha (Voivodeship: 32.80 ha; Poland: 11.32 ha). Farms with an area of up to 10 ha constitute about 50% of the total number of farms. The natural values of rural areas create good conditions for the development of organic farming. There are 53 organic agricultural producers and farms in the county. It should be noted that Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship has great potential for the development of organic farming. Despite this, the share of organic producers in the region in the total number of organic producers in Poland is low and amounted to 10.9% in 2020 (EFRWP. *Directions and opportunities for the development of organic farming in Poland*⁴³). In coastal municipalities, in recent years, the agricultural function has been significantly reduced in favour of tourist and residential development.

⁴¹https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki; <https://analizy.monitorrozwoju.pl/dashboard?city=1234&area=29&subarea=313>

Accessed on 25 August 2024

⁴²<https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/zachodniopomorskie#rejestr-region> Accessed on 25 August 2024

⁴³ <https://efrwp.pl/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/kierunki-rozwoju-golnictwa-ekologicznego-w-polsce.pdf> Accessed on 24 August 2024

4.4 Labour market

The number of economically active people in Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship in 2022 was 733 thousand, of which women accounted for 45.83%. The number of economically inactive population in the province was 573 thousand, including 60.03% women. In 2023, compared to 2022, there is a decrease in the number of economically inactive people (by 0.7%), which should be considered a positive phenomenon. In the group of the economically inactive, every third person had at most lower secondary education or did not have school education. Almost every second economically active person had a university degree (GUS, Poland in numbers, 2023). The level of economic activity determined by the **economic activity rate** in 2022 in Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship was 56.2% and it did not differ significantly for the national average. The higher the value of the economic activity rate, the greater the proportion of people of working age who are professionally employed. On the other hand, the **employment rate** (determines what percentage of the population of working age is working. In Poland, it is calculated for the population of men between 18 and 64 years of age and the population of women between 18 and 59 years of age) in the voivodeship was 55.4%. The highest employment rate in the province was recorded for men (62.6%).

In 2022, there were 867 unemployed persons per 1000 employed persons in Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship, with a greater burden of employed persons in rural areas than in urban areas (1137 persons compared to 761, respectively). There were six economically inactive men for every ten economically active men, and ten for women (GUS, Poland in numbers, 2023).

The negative balance of arrivals and departures indicates that both Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship and the Gryfice County are characterized by a low power of attracting labour from the neighbouring areas. The low supply of jobs or its lack in the region, county and adjacent areas results in an impulse to initiate work-related population flows.

Table 4. Availability of the labour market in the region in 2022

Specification	Gryfice powiat	Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship	Poland
Number of enterprises	8,667	245,268	2,349,800
Number of newly registered enterprises	575	17,409	385,966
Number of enterprises deleted from the register of entities conducting business activity	381	11,858	224,987
Number of economically active inhabitants per 1000 inhabitants	150	222	259
Labour Force Participation Rate (BAEL)	-	56.2%	58.2%
Employment rate (BAEL)	-	55.4%	56.5%
Type of business by sector (2023)	2.5% agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing; 21.3% industry	2.1% agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing; 24.5% industry and construction; 73,4% other activities	1.4% agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing; 22.7% industry and

	and construction; 76,2% other activities		construction; 75.9% other activities
Employment by sector (2021)	21.0% agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing; 20.2% industry and construction; 21.1% service; 2.7% financial sector	7.2% agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing; 29.0% industry and construction; 25.5% service; 2.8% financial sector	10.3% agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing; 30.1% industry and construction; 23.4% service; 3.6% financial sector

Source: <https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/#rejestr-regon-w-pigulce> <https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/zachodniopomorskie#rynek-pracy> <https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/zachodniopomorskie#rejestr-regon-w-pigulce> https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki#rejestr-regon https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki#rynek-pracy (Accessed on 24 August 2024).

According to the data of the Poviát Employment Office in Gryfice, in 2021 a total of 2258 job offers were submitted in the poviát (470 more than in 2021), including 1734 (76.79%) for non-subsidized job offers, 524 for subsidized job offers (23.21%). The majority (80.95%) of the offers concerned taking up work in the private sector. The most frequently sought after were cashier/salesman, construction worker, or manual worker (Report on the activities of the Poviát Employment Office⁴⁴). Job offers submitted by employers to the labour office may be the result of a high demand for manual workers and at the same time a lack of people willing to perform basic physical work, which has been recorded for a long time not only in the poviát or in voivodeship, but also in Poland. Performing these jobs is not always associated with high earnings, bonuses or benefits for the employee. In addition, there is a general belief in society that physical work is slightly worse.

Changes in the population structure will have major economic consequences for the region. There may also be mismatches in the labour market in terms of sectors or occupations (for example, due to increased demand for health care and social care workers, related to the increase in the population aged 65+, and above all 80+), which may result from changes in the consumption structure (Janicka et al., 2015). The shrinking labour force is a consequence of the ageing of the population, which is a trend visible not only in Poland but also in other EU countries.

4.5 Institutional setting

The poviát is responsible for the maintenance and development of the material base of schools and educational institutions. This responsibility concerns the economic dimension and is a certain obligation to the county community in the field of creating an educational system that will create a chance for personal development for the residents. Education at every level is essential for shaping entrepreneurial, innovative and creative attitudes in the region.

⁴⁴ <https://gryfice.praca.gov.pl/> Accessed 10 July 2024

In 2022, there were **12 kindergartens** in the Gryfice powiat (Voivodeship: 465), including one special kindergarten (Voivodeship: 17), attended by 1,235 children. 16.4% of the inhabitants of the Gryfice powiat in the age of potential education (3-24 years) belong to the range of 3-6 years - pre-school education (16.6% among girls and 16.3% among boys). 780 per thousand children of preschool age attend preschool education institutions (Voivodeship: 900; Poland: 927). In 2018, there were 1.34 preschool children per place in a preschool education institution (Voivodeship: 0.97; Poland: 0.89). There is one nursery, and one kids club in the county⁴⁵.

There are **22 primary schools** in the powiat, including **two special schools** for children and youth, which provide education at the primary level (Voivodeship: 470, including 55 special schools)⁴⁶. The main task of special schools is to create the best possible conditions for children with disabilities to develop, overcome barriers, learn to be independent and be an active member of society.

The gross enrolment rate for primary schools (availability and quality of primary school education) is 91.33% (96.34% in the Voivodeship; Poland 95.96%). In the 3-24 age group, 28.1% of the population is enrolled at the primary level (7-12 years) (27.8% among girls and 28.3% among boys). There are 17.0 pupils per 1 class in primary schools (Voivodeship: 17.6; Poland: 17). In addition, there are **8 general secondary schools** for young people in the powiat (144 in the province), including 3 for adults, with 1,296 students (725 women and 571 men). In 2022, 258 graduates were registered. The pass rate of the End of Education (Matura exam) in these schools is 89.10% (Poland: 84.4%). In 2022, 258 graduates were registered. The enrolment rate for a general secondary school is 46.25%. The number of people who have completed their education in high school per people of working age is 7.7. In the Gryfice powiat there are **4 Technical Schools** (Voivodeship: 91), in which 466 students (196 women and 270 men) studied in 29 departments. There are 16.1 students per class (Voivodeship: 23.8; Poland: 24.9). In 2022, 73 graduates were registered. Education is also provided in **6 stage I. sectoral vocational schools** (Voivodeship: 96). In 2022, there were 337 students (118 women and 219 men). There are 16.9 students per 1 class (Voivodeship: 20.2; Poland: 21.00). The number of people who have completed education in a technical secondary school per person of working age is 2.65. In the 3-24 age group, 12.7% of the population is educated at the upper secondary level (16-18 years) (12.7% among girls and 12.6% among boys). There are 23.1 pupils per 1 class in general education schools (Voivodeship: 25; Poland: 26.5). There are 16.9 pupils per class in stage I sectoral vocational schools. There are 16.1 pupils per class in technical secondary schools for young people. In the age range corresponding to education in higher education (19-24 years) there are 28.2% of the inhabitants of the Gryfice powiat in the age of potential education (28.1% of women and 28.4% of men). There are also 2 post-secondary schools in the powiat (including a college for employees of special services). The majority of students are women (85%). In addition, there is one university (non-public) in the county – Zachodniopomorskie Business School in Gryfice.

⁴⁵https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki#edukacja-i-szkolnictwo Accessed on 5 July 2024

⁴⁶https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki#edukacja-i-szkolnictwo Accessed on 5 July 2024

About 47% of the total population of the Gryfice powiat, and thus a similar percentage of children, live within a 15-minute walk to primary school. Another 35% of children can reach primary school within 15 minutes by bike. Within the range of an acceptable 15-minute commute to school by car or school bus, more than 99% of the county's residents live. Since 2012, there has been a growing trend in this area – the competitiveness of educational institutions, as well as increased mobility of both students and parents ready to take their children to other schools far from their place of residence.

In 2022, there were **14 public libraries and branches** in the Gryfice County (Voivodeship: 348) with a book collection of 186,817 volumes and **1 scientific library/research** branch with a book collection of 24,911 volumes, including special volumes: 164. There were 93 readers (active borrowers) during the year. In these libraries, a total of 3 computers are available to readers. Only one of the libraries offers the possibility of placing orders for library materials remotely.⁴⁷

Culture plays a very important role in the processes of socialization. Cultural activity is a key area through which social competences can be shaped. Cultural activity creates an opportunity to build social bonds, integrate and take joint action to build your local spaces. In the county, social life is concentrated in cultural houses (clubs), which conduct various forms of activity of the residents. **Houses and cultural centres, clubs and community centres** in 2022 in the Gryfice powiat: **45** (public: 44, private: 1) (Voivodeship: 327), including facilities adapted for disabled people in wheelchairs: 0. In the Gryfice powiat, **4 institutions have auditoriums**. Residents can also belong to various **circles/clubs/sections**, of which there are **38** in the powiat (18 art, 8, music 3, photography and film 1, literature 2, senior/University of the Third Age 3, other 3), gathering 38 over 500 members. The period of the highest intensity of cultural life in the county falls mainly on the summer months and is concentrated mainly in tourist destinations⁴⁸.

In rural areas, village community centres, which are **local cultural centres**, play an important role in activating residents. There are several village community centers in Gryfice powiat, and their number is constantly changing due to new investments (currently, their number is estimated at over 38). Village community centres may be administered by a cultural center. Sometimes, this function is taken over by the commune office or non-governmental organizations – associations and foundations. Village community centers are usually managed by community center carers, who receive symbolic remuneration for their work. In most cases, village community centers operate autonomously, without common regulations for all such facilities in a given commune. In such places, general development activities for children are organized to develop children's interests and skills, manual and handicraft classes are organized for the elderly. The cultural centres are also a place for meetings and integration, where residents can meet, exchange experiences and integrate. They play an important role in shaping the rural community. Acting as a place open to everyone, they foster building bonds and solidarity between residents. However, it should be emphasized that the functioning of rural community centres

⁴⁷https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki#kultura-rekreacja-i-noclegi Accessed on 10 July 2024

⁴⁸https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/powiat_gryficki#kultura-rekreacja-i-noclegi Accessed on 10 July 2024

largely depends on the involvement of the local community, appropriate support from local authorities and financing.

There is **1 Independent Public Complex of Health Care Facilities** in Gryfice in the poviát. The hospital provides medical services for both the residents of the Gryfice poviát and neighbouring counties. The potential of the facility is not used. The indicator determining the level of availability of higher-level (hospital) medical services (number of beds in general hospitals per 1000 inhabitants) is 4.8. The level of availability of medical services is low. **The number of doctors and dentists working by primary workplace per 1000 inhabitants of the county in 2021 was 2.8.** In addition, residents can use **38 clinics located** in the poviát. There are **20 pharmacies and 3 pharmacy points** in the poviát. There are **34 people per 1 pharmacy**⁴⁹. Residents of the county can use medical facilities located throughout the region. In total, there were 44 hospitals in Zachodniopomorskie in 2021, with the number of beds per 10 thousand population 42.7. There are also 39 health resort treatment i.e. sanatoria and hospitals, with 6.5 beds per 1000 population. In addition, there are 941 clinics in the province (5.7 per 10 thousand population). There are also 82 emergency medical teams in the region. The number of working doctors per 10 thousand population in 2022 was 32.1 (9th place in the country), compared to 2021, a decrease of 0.3% was recorded. The number of nurses and midwives per 10 thousand population reached 54.4 (14th place in the country) compared to 2021 there was a decrease of 0.2%⁵⁰.

Table 5. Medical care entities in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship in 2022

Specification	Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship
Number of hospitals	44
the number of beds per 10 thousand population	42.7
health resort treatment i.e. sanatoria and hospitals	39
the number of beds per 1000 population	6.5
Number of outpatient clinics	941
Number of clinics per 10 thousand inhabitants	5.7
Number of emergency medical teams	82
Number of working doctors per 10,000 inhabitants	32.1

Source: *Report on the state of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship for 2023.*
https://baw2.wzp.pl/UMWZP/document/7772/Uchwala-862_24 Accessed on 5 July 2024

The road system in the Gryfice poviát enables efficient access to larger urban centres within the county. At the same time, it should be noted that the existing road system does not meet the needs of the growing car traffic and the functioning of public transport in rural areas. The existing road network with low technical parameters and largely poor condition does not guarantee service at an appropriate level.

⁴⁹https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/poviat_gryficki#kultura-rekreacja-i-noclegi Accessed on 10 July 2024

⁵⁰https://baw2.wzp.pl/UMWZP/document/7772/Uchwala-862_24 Accessed on 5 July 2024

Figure 7. Road system of the Gryfice poviát

*Explanation: red - national road; yellow - regional road; green - county road; grey - municipal road.

Source: Diagnostic report. A portrait of the partnership of the Gryfice poviát. Integrated Territorial Investment Instrument.⁵¹

Residents have the opportunity to use public transport – bus and minibuss transport, rail. Public transport organised by communes located in the poviát is mainly related to the organisation of school transport and takes place on routes subordinated to the transport of pupils. There are 7.3 public buses per 1000 inhabitants (voivodship: 3.9; Poland: 3.4). The system of road passenger transport is still dominated by public transport organised by private carriers licensed by the authorities of the relevant local government level (permits for the operation of transport lines are issued). Despite this, the inhabitants of the countryside point to problems with reaching the city (e.g. Gryfice, Trzebiatów), both in the context of the insufficient offer of car and bus transport, as well as the lack of bicycle paths that would allow access to the city from the nearest towns. The current public transport network in rural areas is optimised in a commercial sense, but not in a social sense. This means that more and more people in rural areas have increasingly poor access to public transport services and related mobility. There is one railway line in the county. Train connections take place at intervals of 2 hours on average, giving the opportunity to adjust the travel schedule to the needs of residents and tourists. Due to the high tourist traffic (especially in coastal municipalities), there is a very strong seasonality in public transport, both in timetables and in the number of passengers carried.

⁵¹Available online: https://cwd.info.pl/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/ZACH_KAM_raport_diagnostyczny_2022.10.31.pdf Accessed on 27 August 2024

The role of the maritime transport service centre in the poviát is currently fulfilled by the seaport in Mrzeżyno. The port has a strictly defined status of a fishing port – due to this, the traffic of fishing vessels takes place here. The port in Mrzeżyno has the status of a maritime border crossing, which covers cargo traffic by fishing vessels.

The length of the bicycle paths is 41 km. Bicycle paths per 10 thousand km² in the poviát account for 399.6 km (for the voivodeship 542.9 km; Poland 633.6 km), while the length of bicycle paths per 10 thousand population is 7.2 km (for the voivodeship 7.6 km; Poland 5.3 km).

The Gryfice poviát is one of the municipalities with a well-developed telephone network. There are 39 BTS stations in the county, covering the area of the county, therefore it allows for universal availability of mobile telephony. However, the problem is access to the IT network in rural areas (lack of independent operators and the possibility of connecting to the broadband network). Hence the need to expand the broadband network to other towns, and in particular to towns where school centres operate. Equally important as the development of infrastructure is the development of electronic services for the public in order to facilitate contact with the administration, as well as the creation of computer labs with access to the broadband network in school facilities.

4.5.1 Local policies and instruments

Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship's rural policy, which complements national ones, focuses on regional-level competencies, objectives, and intervention tools. It aims to boost economic activity, entrepreneurship, job creation, improve business conditions, and support collective economic initiatives. This activity remains complementary to initiatives undertaken at the national level. It is stimulated by regulations relating to specific issues or regulations within the sectoral policies of the state (Eregion WZP. Rural policy.⁵²).

Rural areas play an important role in the current policies of the region. As part of the Development Strategy of Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship until 2030, rural development is one of the key priorities. The document stresses that rural development is impossible without urban centres playing a leading role. The activities included in the strategy are to contribute to sustainable development, taking into account the specificity of these areas, their potential and problems. Actions aimed at eliminating problems in rural areas include, among others:

- counteracting the outflow of young people by improving conditions on the local labour market and creating attractive places to live,
- support for access to public services and local infrastructure, in particular in former state-owned farming areas,
- targeting activities aimed at ensuring that people in rural areas have access to public services of an appropriate standard,

⁵² http://www.ereqion.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/polityka_obszarow_wiejskich_ost.pdf Accessed on 10 July 2024

- counteracting various forms of social exclusion and social reintegration of people who are already excluded.

In the document "Outline of the study on the development of rural areas and agriculture in Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship until 2030", key strategies and activities focus on improving the quality of life, entrepreneurship development, infrastructure and environmental protection. Main areas of support:

- infrastructure development – investments in technical infrastructure, including municipal roads, gas, water supply and sewage networks. Striving to improve drinking water quality and reduce pollution. Modernization of energy distribution, with a preference for renewable energy sources,
- support for entrepreneurship – development of non-agricultural economic activity and creation of new jobs. Supporting local agricultural markets and developing the agri-food industry,
- agricultural development – promotion of organic farming, as well as a multifunctional and sustainable model of agriculture,
- development of rural tourism – supporting the creation of an attractive tourist offer, including workshops and cultural events,
- rural revitalization – improving public spaces, infrastructure and living conditions,
- education and human capital development – investments in education and training to develop scientific, technical and managerial skills,
- counteracting social exclusion – support for groups at risk of social exclusion, including the long-term unemployed, young people and people with disabilities. Activities in this area include: professional activation programmes and activities to improve professional qualifications; providing access to care services, counselling and psychological support; educational, sports and cultural programmes aimed at young people; equalizing educational opportunities in villages and small towns, as well as adapting fields of education to the needs of the labour market; support for local initiatives, development of micro-enterprises and creation of new jobs, including non-agricultural jobs; improve public space, infrastructure, as well as the aesthetics and values of the countryside.

The directions of the planned interventions in the field of improving the socio-economic situation in the municipalities of Zachodniopomorskie have been developed on the basis of the delimitation of the region and the designation of Special Inclusion Zones in it (Special Inclusion Zone in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship and the planned directions of intervention activities⁵³). In accordance with the Development Strategy of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship until 2030, the

⁵³ https://wzs.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/delimitacja_ssw_w_ramach_rpo_wz_01_04_2019.pdf Accessed on 27 August 2024

Special Inclusion Zone is an area of strategic intervention of the region (Development Strategy of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship until 2030⁵⁴). The delimitation of the Special Inclusion Zone in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship and the planned directions of intervention activities were adopted by Resolution No. 1411/23 of September 1, 2023 by the Management Board of Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship. The document Concept of Spatial Development of the Country 2030 indicates that in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship there is a special accumulation of areas characterized by negative features determining development opportunities. These are in particular rural areas that require support for development processes. Low spatial accessibility to the main regional and national growth centres and insufficient access to basic public services result in progressive depopulation, high unemployment, low level of entrepreneurship and progressive social exclusion. Four out of six municipalities of the powiat (Płoty, Brojce, Gryfice and Karnice) have been classified as areas of special needs and urgent intervention. These municipalities accumulate most of the problems that significantly affect the social exclusion of their residents.

Table 6. Occurrence of deficits in municipalities of Gryfice powiat

Municipalities of Gryfice powiat	economic potential	demography	technical infrastructure	accessibility to public services	poverty	development and investment
Płoty	+	+	+	+	+	+
Brojce	+	-	+	+	+	+
Karnice	-	+	+	+	-	-
Gryfice	-	-	+	-	+	-
Rewal	-	+	-	-	-	-
Trzebiatów	-	-	-	-	+	-

Source: <https://wzs.wzp.pl/programowanie-rozwoju/specjalna-strefa-wlaczenia/biezace-informacje-o-ssw/delimitacja-specjalnej-strefy-wlaczenia-na-obszarze-województwa-zachodniopomorskiego-oraz-planowane> (Accessed on 19 June 2024).

The regional government will take action to build and strengthen cooperation networks, especially in rural areas of the region, based on the institutional solutions of Local Action Groups and revitalization programs. This is aimed at supporting the development of rural areas, and in particular social revival through a comprehensive solution to problems in the social, spatial and functional, technical, economic and environmental areas. Revitalization, as a process of bringing an area out of a state of crisis, is one of the municipalities' own tasks. In 2022, 1440 municipalities (58.2% of all municipalities in Poland) carried out revitalization activities. The total area of degraded areas (i.e., areas with a high concentration of social phenomena) in Poland in 2022 amounted to 3958.3 thousand hectares. The share of the degraded area in the total area of the country was 12.7%. The largest degraded areas were designated in urban-rural and rural communes (on average per one commune – 3.1 thousand hectares each). In Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship, the share of the degraded area in the total area of the voivodeship amounted to 21.3%. Over 83.2% of communes carried out revitalization activities. In terms of area, the largest degraded areas have been designated in Zachodniopomorskie (5.2

⁵⁴ http://eregion.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/srwz_2030.pdf Accessed on 27 August 2024

thousand hectares per one commune). In the area of MAP operation, all communes carried out revitalization activities. In the structure of projects planned in the revitalization programs in Zachodniopomorskie, over 40% was a social sector. Numerous activities are also planned in the spatial-functional and technical areas (CSO, 2024).

There are 13 Local Action Groups (LAGs) in Zachodniopomorskie. These are highly professionalized organizations, shaping local development strategies in close cooperation with rural residents and their representatives. Within the framework of the two EU financial perspectives 2007-2013 and 2014-2020, through the LAGs, Zachodniopomorskie rural areas received a total of nearly EUR 69.9 million. There were 2,826 aid agreements were signed. Only under the previous perspective, thanks to the support granted, 535 new private enterprises, 835 jobs, 392 tourist and recreational infrastructure facilities were created, and 199 such facilities were modernized. It was possible to develop 173 enterprises, 492 training courses were organized, 51 monuments were subjected to conservation or restoration works and 398 events were organized⁵⁵. The LAG is a voluntary, self-governing, permanent association of natural and legal persons, including local government units, aimed at acting for the development of rural areas, and in particular: integrating and activating communities with particular emphasis on young people up to 25 years of age, seniors and people in a disadvantaged situation, undertaking initiatives and activities aimed at stimulating the activity of local communities, promotion of rural areas, providing support to residents in the preparation of projects and obtaining funds for their implementation, including aid programs and conducting training activities. The members of the Local Action Group are representatives of local socio-economic interest groups who represent the interests of the following sectors: public (commune, powiat, village head), social (residents, non-governmental organizations, churches and religious associations, trade unions, socio-professional organizations of farmers, including rural housewives' associations, other voluntary associations and civic movements) and economic (entities conducting economic activity, including social enterprises and farmers, as well as the economic self-government). There are various forms of support for LAGs in Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship, including:

- financial support under the Rural Development Programme for the implementation of investment, training and educational projects promoting local culture and heritage and support for entrepreneurship,
- organizational and advisory support offered by various institutions, including Social Economy Support Centres and the Regional Centre for Social Policy.

The implementation of the initiative for rural development in the area of MAP is carried out, among others, by the association: Local Action Group "Gryflandia" based in Gryfice⁵⁶. The Association carries out activities aimed at the development of entrepreneurship, improving access to small public infrastructure; protection of the cultural and natural heritage of the Polish countryside; strengthening

⁵⁵<https://www.wzp.pl/biuro-prasowe/biuro-prasowe/aktualnosci/zachodniopomorska-wies-otwiera-sie-na-nowa-perspektywe-lokalne-grupy-dzialania-z-umowami> Accessed on 26 August 2024

⁵⁶<https://lqdgryflandia.pl>

education programs for leaders of public and social life or activation support for families, communities and people at risk of poverty or social exclusion, which are financed by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027) and the European Social Fund+ (European Funds for Western Pomerania 2021-2027).

Support for rural areas is also implemented from the funds financed by the Marshal of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship as part of the "**Village Grants**" and "**Beautiful Zachodniopomorskie Village**" competitions. The aim of the competition is to support the development of local democracy and civil society and to strengthen the identity and integration of the local community. Another support is the "Social Activist Program", under which tasks in the field of ecology and youth are financed. The program is financed by the Koszalin Regional Development Agency S.A.

An important system of support for local initiatives, which enables the implementation of socially important projects in rural areas, is the village fund, which is a form of participatory budgeting. The village fund is a set aside financial resources in the commune budget, which are guaranteed to villages for the implementation of projects aimed at improving their living conditions. Village meeting – i.e. the inhabitants of a given village decide what the above-mentioned funds are to be used for.

It is worth noting that social initiatives in rural areas are also supported by other non-profit institutions. An example is the Association with an idea. The members are young people of many professions, and passions. This multithreading allows them to operate in many areas. They are interested in sport, ecology, development of civil society, education of children, youth and seniors.⁵⁷

Another initiative supporting the development of rural areas is the activity of the Rural Housewives' Associations. They cooperate with many local and non-local actors and contribute to the inclusion of rural residents in the process of creating and implementing public services. They are an important element of civil society and are an expression of involvement in social activities, mainly of women.

An important institution at the national and regional level dealing with the problems of rural development is the **National Rural Network**.⁵⁸ The aim of the Network is to increase the participation of stakeholders in the implementation of rural development initiatives, or to activate rural residents to undertake initiatives aimed at social inclusion, in particular the elderly, young people, the disabled, national minorities and other socially excluded people. The National Rural Network is open. The Network is open to all actors involved in rural development. The participation of partners in the Network is ensured by the central unit (at the national level) and regional units, regional working groups and the NRN Working Group at the national level. The network brings together representatives of various sectors: public, social and private from various levels of management. The NRN partner database of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship includes around 220 entities ready to cooperate for rural development.

⁵⁷<https://www.facebook.com/stowarzyszenieZPomyslem/>

⁵⁸<https://ksow.pl>

5. Vulnerability and social exclusion in the Gryfice region

5.1 Social exclusion and poverty

In 2021, 49.2% of households in Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship rated their financial situation as good or rather good (Poland 53.0%). The largest number of households, both in the voivodeship (43.5%) and in the country (41.8%), assessed their financial situation as average (Gryfice Commune. Financial situation of households in 2021⁵⁹).

The population living in Polish regions where State Agricultural Farms operated before the transformation period (these regions include Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship) are particularly vulnerable to poverty and destitution. For these regions, a particular threat to functioning in society is the so-called inheritance of poverty. In these families, there is an "intergenerational transmission of conditions" (Tarkowska, 2024⁶⁰). In families of this type, there are no aspirations to get out of poverty. Young people, due to low ambitions in science, do not achieve a high level of education. The aspect of education is pushed into the background. The educational deficit causes low competitiveness of young people on the labour market. In addition, early parenthood, which often occurs, prevents further professional development and the acquisition of new qualifications (Sierpowska, 2017).

The percentage of people in households in extreme poverty in 2022 in the North-West macro-region was 3.5% (Poland 4.7%). The extent of extreme poverty in this macro-region compared to other Polish macro-regions was the lowest. Compared to 2021, it decreased by 0.2 pp. The basis for determining the extreme poverty line in Poland is the subsistence minimum estimated by the Institute of Labour and Social Affairs and relating to household expenditures. The minimum subsistence category designates a very low level of needs satisfaction. The EAPN Poland Report shows that in 2022 compared to 2021, the extent of extreme poverty among children and seniors increased in Poland. However, the number of children in extreme poverty increased by tens of thousands – by about 26 thousand to 396 thousand compared to 371 thousand in 2021 (an increase from 5.3% to 5.7%). The social and material deprivation of children in families increased even more – by almost 68 thousand (from 4.3% to 5.3%), which accounted for 368 thousand children. Extreme poverty in families with children with disabilities also increased significantly – from 5.2% to 6.7%. The number of extremely poor seniors increased by about 14 thousand – from 272 thousand in 2021 to 287 thousand in 2022 (an increase from 3.8% to 3.9%). Relative poverty decreased to a small extent – from 12.2% to 11.8% – there were about 4.5 million people in this situation. On the other hand, about 15.4 million Polish inhabitants remain socially excluded, living below the subsistence minimum (a decrease in the rate from 42.4% to 40.7%)⁶¹.

⁵⁹ <http://spow.gryfice.ibip.pl/public/getFile?id=1022348> Accessed on 27 August 2024

⁶⁰ <https://magazynkontakt.pl/prof-tarkowska-ubostwo-bez-miary/> Accessed on 25 August 2024

⁶¹ https://www.eapn.org.pl/eapn/uploads/2023/10/poverty_watch_23_v12_10_v2_ost.pdf. Accessed on 25 August 2024

The percentage of people in relatively poor households was 9.8% (11.0% in 2021) (Poland 11.8%). This value was similar to the relative poverty rate recorded in other Polish macro-regions. The relative poverty line in Poland is assumed at the level of 50% of the amount that households in Poland spend on average per month, which is a level of consumption significantly different from the average level. In this approach, people and families are considered poor whose standard of living is much lower than that of other members of a given society. This type of poverty cannot be eradicated, it can only be reduced, among other things, by eliminating inequalities in the distribution of income (Sierpowska, 2017). The north-western macro-region also recorded the lowest percentage of people in households who experienced deprivation compared to other regions of Poland (33.6%) (GUS 2023. Poverty in Poland in 2021 and 2022).

In Zachodniopomorskie, as many as 57,861 households and homeless people benefited from social assistance in 2022 (Poland: 1,302,265). Most of them were people in multi-person households, their number amounted to 34578 (Poland 862,344). Men (30,341 people) used social assistance much more often than women (27,520) and people living in cities. Compared to the previous year, the number of social assistance beneficiaries in the voivodship decreased compared to 2021 by 0.4 pp (3.9% to 3.5%) (Poland: 3.7% to 3.4% – a decrease by 0.3 pp).

The number of households benefiting from social assistance with income below the criterion (in 2022, the amount of this criterion for a person in a family was EUR 139, and for a person running a household alone was EUR 180) in Poland in 2022 amounted to 422,276, of which 248,452 (58.83%) were people living in cities and 173,824 (41.17%) were residents of rural areas. In the Zachodniopomorskie 19,228 households benefited from social assistance, 11,543 (60.03%) were urban households and 7,685 (39.97%) were rural households. **The most common reasons for granting social benefits** in households receiving social assistance were health problems and unemployment (GUS, 2023. Beneficiaries of community social assistance in 2022.).

In the Gryfice powiat in 2022, the number of people receiving social assistance (households and homeless people) was 2,676. The number of households using social assistance in 2022 was 1,368. Compared to 2013, this number increased by over 1,400 households. Over the past few years, the number of families in the powiat that have been granted assistance due to homelessness has slightly decreased (a decrease from 80 in 2014 to 74 in 2022) and the number of families that have been granted assistance due to unemployment has decreased significantly (a decrease from 1,493 in 2014 to 399 in 2022)⁶².

An important aspect of improving the quality of life of residents is access to housing resources. The lack of sufficient housing resources results in the lack of independence of young people and their lack of leaving their family homes. Young adults living with their parents are referred to as nesters. In 2018, more than one in three people (36%) aged 25 to 34 in Poland lived with their parents and did not start their own family, thus being included in the population of the so-called nesters. A greater

⁶² <https://analizy.monitorrozwoju.pl/dashboard?city=1234&area=33&subarea=370> Accessed on 25 August 2024

concentration of nesters occurs in peripheral areas. In the Gryfice powiat, the share of nesters in the total population aged 25-34 years is between 30-40%, which is a result close to the average for the entire voivodeship. In Poland, in 2022, one in three people aged 25-34 was a nester (GUS 2020 Generation of Young adults Living with their Barents in Poland)⁶³.

5.2 Labour market

The factor that builds the competitiveness of the region is the education of its inhabitants. Compared to the national average, the inhabitants of the Gryfice powiat have a lower level of education. Compared to the data in the entire province and the country, the powiat is characterized by a much lower percentage of people with higher education and a much higher percentage of people with basic vocational education. Among women living in the Gryfice powiat, the largest percentage has general secondary and higher education. Men most often have basic vocational education (32.40%) and secondary vocational education (16.90%). This means that women in the Gryfice powiat are better educated than men.⁶⁴

Table 7. Percentage of population by education level in the region in 2021

Education	Gryfice powiat			Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship			Poland		
	total	women	men	total	women	men	total	women	men
Higher	16.6	20.3	12.3	23.4	27.1	19.3	25.2	29.1	20.8
General secondary education	16.2	17.7	15.1	13.1	14.9	11.1	11.9	13.7	9.8
Post-secondary	3.8	4.8	2.3	3.4	4.6	2.0	3.3	4.5	2.0
Secondary vocational	16	15.2	16.9	19.1	17.5	21.00	20.0	17.9	22.4
Essential professional	24.8	17.7	32.4	20.6	15.1	26.6	21.2	16.1	26.9
Grammar school	3.3	3.0	3.7	3.4	2.8	4.0	3.0	2.5	3.6
Elementary completed	15.7	17.7	13.7	13.8	14.8	12.6	12.3	13.3	11.1
Elementary incomplete and without education	3.5	3.5	3.7	3.3	3.2	3.4	3.1	3.0	3.3

Source: <https://www.polskawliczbach.pl/#edukacja-i-szkolnictwo> (Accessed on 29 June 2024).

Unemployment in the region is a big problem that affects a large part of the society. Statistics on unemployment significantly distort the picture of this phenomenon due to the high degree of the so-called latent unemployment and the prevalence of "undeclared work" (Development Strategy of the Gryfice County for 2020-2030⁶⁵). Therefore, the level of unemployment recorded in the statistics of labour market institutions may differ from the actual number of unemployed people. **The registered unemployment rate** (the ratio of the number of registered unemployed to the economically active population (the labour force of a given population) in the Gryfice powiat in 2022 was 7.40% and it was

⁶³<https://stat.gov.pl/statystyki-eksperymentalne/jakosc-zycia/pokolenie-gniazdownikow-w-polsce,6,2.html>. Accessed on 23 July 2024.

⁶⁴<https://svs.stat.gov.pl/3706/3/183>; <https://www.wup.pl/pl/dla-instytucji/statystyka-badania-i-analiza/statystyki-rynku-pracy/> Accessed on 29 June 2024.

⁶⁵ <https://www.gryfice.pl/pliki/STRATEGIA-POVIAT-GRYFICKI-2020.pdf> Accessed on 29 June 2024

higher than the average for the voivodeship (6.70%) and the country (5.8%). Women in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship, including the Gryfice powiat, have a much worse situation on the labour market than men, despite statistically better education. The percentage of registered unemployed women in the total number of unemployed was 66.17% (voivodship: 56.3%). Compared to 2021, the situation of women in the labour market has improved. The number of registered unemployed women in Gryfice powiat decreased by 12% (Voivodship: decrease by 6.9%) (WUP, 2022a). As the data indicate, women in the Gryfice powiat are well educated, but often their knowledge and skills acquired during education remain largely outside the labour market. Which is a very negative phenomenon indicating that the potential of women in the labour market is not used (WUP, 2022b).

Unemployed people who are in a special situation on the labour market are people who, due to factors such as age, professional qualifications or family status, health condition or other circumstances, have particular difficulties in obtaining employment or other gainful employment (Act on the Promotion of Employment and Labour Market Institutions, Article 49). The unemployed qualified to this group have priority in being referred to participate in special programs. Among the unemployed in a special situation on the labour market, the highest percentage in the Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship and the Gryfice powiat were long-term unemployed (64.93% and 55.47%, respectively). Every third unemployed person in a special situation on the labour market is a person over 50 years of age (voivodeship – 35.74%; powiat – 34.98%). Also, every third unemployed person (33.15%) who are in a special situation on the labour market in the Gryfice powiat is a person under 30 years of age (in the province – 25.89%). In the Gryfice powiat, this percentage constitutes 25.86% of the total number of unemployed people in a special situation on the labour market. The unemployed in a special situation on the labour market constituted over 82.37% of the total registered unemployed in the Zachodniopomorskie, in the Gryfice Powiat this share constituted 76.71%. A low percentage of the total unemployed were people using social assistance benefits. This may be due to the fact that these people rely on state aid, and therefore also have a reduced motivation to take up work. Unfortunately, this may be associated with the emergence of a dangerous phenomenon, which is the long-term dependence of these people on state-guaranteed assistance. Every fifth unemployed person registered in the labour office had at least one child under 6 years of age. This indicates that it is very difficult for these people to enter or return to the labour market. Over 5% of the total number of registered unemployed in the voivodeship and in the powiat were the disabled. It should be noted, however, that an increasing number of employers are looking for employees among people with disabilities, breaking the prevailing stereotypes, in particular the belief that a disabled person will not be able to cope with the job and will additionally require support. In changing the perception of people with disabilities of great importance are numerous activities activating this group of people and the activity of people with disabilities themselves, which in recent years have been increasingly successful in convincing employers to employ them (WUP, 2022c).

The problem of unemployment in the region largely affected **people living in rural areas**. The percentage of people from rural areas in the Gryfice *powiat* (county) in the total number of unemployed in 2022 was 55.47%, including women who accounted for over 59.7%. The percentage of the total number of unemployed people living in rural areas is much higher than the average for

Zachodniopomorskie and for Poland. Ownership transformations and liquidation of state farms carried out in these areas have resulted in much lower employment of people living in rural areas to this day. In addition, the significant distance of these areas, often with a peripheral location from the labour market, translates into problems with looking for a job and professional inactivity⁶⁶. Commuting to work outside the place of residence is sometimes the only way to take up employment. Over the last ten years, the percentage of the unemployed living in rural areas in Zachodniopomorskie has increased (2012 – 54.1%). However, there is no change in the percentage of unemployed women living in rural areas. Not much change in the number of unemployed people from rural areas, including women, was recorded compared to 2021. The number of these unemployed in the province decreased, while the share of unemployed women did not change. In the Gryfice powiat, the share of the unemployed from rural areas in the total number of the unemployed decreased by 4.8%. Despite the decrease in the number of unemployed in rural areas, unfortunately, the share of unemployed women from these areas in the total number of unemployed increased by 1.2 percentage points.

The time of looking for a job has an impact on being unemployed. The **average time of looking for a job in months** in Zachodniopomorskie in 2022 was 6.6 (the average for Polish was 7.4 months). Since 2015, it has decreased significantly (from 12.6 months) (GUS 2023). Selected aspects of the labour market in Poland). Shortening the time of looking for a job may be the result of increased demand for people able to work in the region or an increase in the supply of labour, as a result of, for example, an increase in the amount of real and nominal wages. It should also be noted that in Poland there is a tendency where employers regularly struggle with a shortage of "workforce", hence the time of looking for a job becomes shorter.

5.3 Disadvantaged groups

In Zachodniopomorskie, including the area of operation of the MAP, **there are various groups at risk of exclusion**, lack of participation or inability to participate in important spheres of collective life: social, economic, political and cultural, as well as normal activities characteristic of a given society (Frąckiewicz, 2005). The long-term unemployed and young people living in rural areas and small towns belonging to the so-called post-state farm areas can be considered as the most at risk of exclusion. Currently, a significant part of post-state farm areas is perceived as problem areas. The changes that have taken place in these areas over the last three decades, and the resulting increase in disparities in socio-economic development, have significantly separated them from other parts of the regions and the whole country⁶⁷. As Czerwińska-Jaśkiewicz and Zarębski (2021) notes, the collapse of state-owned farms and the low participation of the private sector in non-agricultural activities of the economy contributed to the weakening of the demand side of the labour market. A barrier to active job search, especially for residents of isolated post-state farm estates, is the lack of adequate transport, as well as its cost. Similar difficulties are also faced by students who want to study (Urbanik, 2008). Young people have worse opportunities or no choice of a school with a specific profile near their place of residence,

⁶⁶ <https://www.wup.pl/pl/dla-instytucji/statystyka-badania-i-analiza/analizy-i-opracowania/2022-rok-analizy/> Accessed on 24 August 2024

⁶⁷ https://partnerstwo.home.pl/crsq/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/KZ_2020_grudzien-1.pdf Accessed on 25 August 2024

in addition, there are problems with commuting to schools with an appropriate profile (in line with expectations) (Matyjas, 2012). From the research of M. Pokrzywa (2014) shows that the lack of access to educational institutions may be the cause of faster termination of educational careers and the related lower chances on the labour market. Also, obtaining higher education for young people from peripheral areas is usually associated with high costs, forced by the need to change their place of residence or commute to larger urban centres. The last dozen or so years have been a period of limited transport and public services in peripheral areas. In Poland, we are also dealing with the closure of transport connections due to their deficit. This generally applies to connections with centres that are at a lower level of economic development and poorer. In their place, there are private connections (bus and car), but they often lack a system of discounted tickets. Difficult access to public or private transport, long travel time to larger urban centres, where most institutions are located (e.g. secondary schools and universities), limits the life chances of young people. In addition, local communities of post-state farm areas are characterized by low social capital and a weak tendency to self-fulfilment (Rosner, 2005). It is worrying that undesirable attitudes are becoming perpetuated among successive generations living in these areas and the phenomenon referred to as "inheriting poverty" (Functional Areas of Supra-Regional Importance⁶⁸). The extremely peripheral location means that the inhabitants struggle with poor access to basic educational or cultural services, which causes their further economic and social marginalization. They often have limited access to information about existing solutions, support opportunities or assistance from institutions operating in the field of the labour market and education. New jobs are rarely created in these areas. Potential investors and entrepreneurs are discouraged by the degree of neglect of the areas. The condition of the roads is bad, there is no appropriate infrastructure that would foster the development of entrepreneurship.

5.4 Access to services

In Zachodniopomorskie, social assistance tasks are carried out at the municipal level by Social Welfare Centres and at the poviast level by the Poviast Family Assistance Centre. In the area of MAP's operation, there is the **Poviast Support Centre in Gryfice**, whose aim is to support people with mental disorders and intellectual disabilities. This centre has 30 places available. There is also a **Crisis Intervention Point in the poviast** and **sheltered housing**. In 2022, specialists were employed as part of the activities of the **Crisis Intervention Point**, who provided assistance to a total of 405 people. In each commune of the county, there are consultation points or other forms of support that provide legal, psychological and therapeutic assistance to those in need, including those affected by domestic violence (Poviast Program for Combating Domestic Violence and Protecting Victims of Domestic Violence for 2023-2027). In the **Poviast Office in Gryfice** there is a **Free Legal Aid Point** and a **Local Support Point for Crime Victims at the Social Welfare Centre in Gryfice**. In 2022, there were 2 social welfare homes in the Gryfice poviast, with a total of 461 places, providing round-the-clock care for adults who, for various reasons, could not function in their family environments. The poviast has 500 places in social welfare homes and 363 places in various types of facilities providing support to children in the crisis of care and educational

⁶⁸ <http://eregion.wzp.pl/obszary/obszary-funkcjonalne-o-znaczeniu-ponadregionalnym> Accessed on 10 July 2024

inefficiency of families. There is also a social integration centre in the county. There is a **Poviat Employment Office** in the poviat. In 2021, 188 people benefited from the career counselling offered as part of the Office's activities, which was 100 people more than in the previous year.

The research conducted among the residents of the Gryfice poviat on the assessment of the situation and the quality and accessibility to public infrastructure and services (e.g. health care, education, accessibility of the labour market), as part of the Development Strategy of the Gryfice Poviat for 2020-2030, shows that every third respondent evaluates the accessibility to public administration rather well, and 6.61% very badly. A survey of poviat residents reveals that 37.00% of respondents offer a rather unfavourable opinion of the local labour market, while 28.19% offer a very negative opinion. In the poviat, the majority of respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the accessibility of healthcare services, with nearly half of them providing a very poor or bad rating. Conversely, the respondents' perception of access to preschool and primary education was positive. Furthermore, the majority of respondents assessed the availability of secondary education as satisfactory, with 35.24% of respondents expressing satisfaction. The condition and accessibility to social infrastructure, including village community centres and similar facilities, was assessed as satisfactory (36.12%) or very good (7.93%). However, over 60% of respondents evaluated the leisure offerings for children and young people as very poor or poor, and 40% of them expressed dissatisfaction with the leisure options available for seniors. Furthermore, more than 70% of respondents assessed the state of local roads as poor or very poor. Furthermore, over 50% of respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the quality of local transportation services. The development of the NGO was assessed very well by only 4.85% of the respondents. Every fourth surveyed resident of the county assessed the general level of satisfaction with life in the county rather well. (Development Strategy of the Gryfice Poviat for 2020-2030).

Conducting public benefit activities, e.g. activities serving humanitarian, charitable and care, scientific and educational purposes) is also the responsibility of social religious entities, i.e. organizational units of the Catholic church and other churches and religious associations. Zachodniopomorskie is the least religious region compared to other provinces in Poland. Statistics show that in 2020, every fifth inhabitant of the province attends mass. This is due to the conditions of the cultural landscape of the Gryfice poviat, resulting from the complicated history that deprived the region of cultural continuity, including attachment to tradition and attachment to the church.

In summary the main factors causing vulnerability to social exclusion in the region include:

- peripheral location of most villages and towns, including the areas of former state farms where the so-called "enclaves of poverty" are formed, these are underinvested areas, with low social capital and poor technical infrastructure,
- underdeveloped public transport system and deficiencies in the network of bicycle paths, limited access to childcare for dependent persons,

- low wealth of the inhabitants – in the region there is a low standard of living, an accumulation of symptoms of bad habits and symptoms of "not coping with the budget", - unattractive conditions for doing business and a decreasing number of start-ups,
- problem with access to the IT network in rural areas (lack of independent operators and the possibility of connecting to the broadband network),
- poverty,
- low level of cultural life, which plays an important role in the social activation of the inhabitants - the period of the highest intensity of cultural life in the county falls mainly in the summer months and is concentrated primarily in tourist destinations,
- limited access to housing,
- low level of education compared to the province and the country, which makes it difficult to take up work,
- the occurrence of the phenomenon of mismatch between potential employees available on the labour market and the needs of employers,
- high share of the unemployed for more than 1 year, including in particular women and people up to 30 years of age,
- limited access to public services related to the daily functioning of local communities (health care, educational services, saturation with entities operating in the field of culture, entertainment, recreation),
- incidental nature of the activities of most associations and foundations, whose role is to support the social activation of residents,
- low share of social economy entities in the social services market in the region.

Social economy entities play an important role in solving urgent challenges related to social exclusion in Zachodniopomorskie. These entities actively contribute to reducing unemployment. For example, **Vocational Activity Centres** offer employment to people with disabilities. In 2020, out of 885 people employed in Vocational Activity Centres, 654 were employees with disabilities. **Social cooperatives** provide opportunities for socially excluded people, especially in rural areas. Social economy entities provide a number of social services and fill the gap in access to these services. For example, **Occupational Therapy Workshops** provide social and vocational rehabilitation to people with disabilities. Foundations organize mobile childcare, seniors, and transport points. **Social Integration Centres** help excluded people return to the labour market. In 2020, 357 people started classes at Social Integration Centres. The largest group were the long-term unemployed (291). Among the people who underwent the reintegration process, 54 were employed, 26 people were sent for a professional internship. **Social Integration Clubs** help the unemployed to obtain employment, offer legal counselling, professional internships or socially useful work. In 2020, 289 people completed classes,

including 36 people who found employment, 21 people were sent to internships, and 67 people were assigned to socially useful work. Social economy entities build new networks of cooperation, connecting non-governmental organizations, local governments, entrepreneurs and local entrepreneurs. The key role in this regard is played **by Social Economy Support Centres and Local Action Groups**. In 2020, thanks to the Social Economy Support Centres, 6 new social enterprises were created, and 65 jobs were created. Local Action Groups help to create and develop small social enterprises in rural areas related to rural tourism and local crafts. Through the organization of local initiatives, trainings and workshops, social economy entities contribute to the increase of the competences of residents, and thus to their more active participation in social life. Regional statistics lack information on the activities of social economy entities in rural areas and what number of socially excluded people from rural areas were beneficiaries of aid from these entities. However, it is known that the number of people using services provided by NGOs or social cooperatives in Zachodniopomorskie is very low. The research conducted for the purposes of the Report on the state of social economy in Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship in 2020 shows that 94.1% of respondents did not use the services of social economy entities in the last two years. This indicates a very small, even imperceptible share of the market of social economy entities, and therefore an underdeveloped sector of social economy in the region. There are several reasons why residents do not use the services and opportunities offered by social economy entities in the region. These include: lack of awareness and knowledge about these organizations and the benefits of their activities; stereotypes and lack of trust – people very often do not believe in the effectiveness of social economy entities; insufficient availability of services, in particular those tailored to actual needs; cultural and social barriers, manifested by a strong tradition of self-sufficiency and low social activity; infrastructural barriers, including the lack of public transport, or problems with access to the Internet and lack of digital competences; insufficient promotion of social economy entities, mainly in peripheral areas.

6. Assets and potentials in the Gryfice region

The geographical, tourist and cultural values of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship, including the Gryfice powiat, are an excellent opportunity for its development. The advantages of the area are bordering with areas of high economic activity (e.g. Szczecin), direct access to the Baltic Sea, largely agricultural nature of the area (low pollution) and good conditions for the development of organic farms, specific microclimate, a large number of monuments and cultural heritage objects that can be used for tourism. One of the greatest potentials of the county remains the resources of the natural environment, including, above all, the attractive tourist coast of the Baltic Sea, which, combined with the growing demand for recreational and tourist services and the use of environmental values (turn towards nature and an active lifestyle), generates the growth of the existing accommodation and service base providing services to domestic and foreign tourists. The offer of public services provides the opportunity to meet basic needs in the field of social services. Well-functioning social organizations, bringing together active representatives of local communities, constitute a potential shaping the level of social capital of the area (Development Strategy of the Gryfice County for 2020-2030; Report on the state of the Gryfice County for 2022). For example: the aim of Association of Social Initiatives "Uśmiech" ("Smile") is to act for the sake of providing help and equalizing opportunities for people in difficult life situations, exposed to existence in areas of pathology, poverty and helplessness; for the Association of Civic Initiatives ZIEMIA GRYFICKA (GRYFICE LAND), the aim of which is to support and undertake activities leading to the development of civil society, increase the activity of local communities in the social and economic sphere⁶⁹. It is also worth noting that communes regularly conduct social consultations and cooperate with non-governmental organizations, which enables residents to actively participate in socio-cultural life. The voivodeship also has good conditions for the functioning of small agri-food processing – thanks to this, it will be possible to use the potential of small farms and provide jobs for the inhabitants of rural areas, in particular women.

At the voivodeship level, a number of strategic documents are in force in the area of shaping social policy, labour market policy, education policy and health care policy, which, through the implementation of the objectives contained therein, will contribute to reducing the vulnerability of society to threats occurring in the region. These are the following:

- Capital and social cohesion policy of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship for 2021-2030.
- Regional program to support the family and the foster care system "Family-Friendly Region" for 2021-2027.
- Zachodniopomorskie Programme for the Development of Social Economy until 2030.
- Regional Programme for Seniors for 2023-2027.
- Regional Programme for Counteracting Domestic Violence and 2021-2025.

⁶⁹ See more: <https://gryfice.eu/wykaz-orgnizacji-pozarzadowych.html>? Accessed on 29 December 2024

- Regional Programme for the Prevention and Resolution of Alcohol Problems and Drug Addiction Prevention for 2022-2026.
- Programme of Cooperation of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship with non-governmental organisations for 2023.
- Regional Action Plan for Employment.
- Labour Market Policy in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship with an outlook to 2030.
- Regional Innovation Strategy of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship 2030.
- Education Policy of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship.
- Capital and Social Cohesion Policy of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship for 2021-2030.
- Implementation Programme for the Voivodeship Health Protection Policy.
- Voivodeship Transformation Plan for Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship for 2022-2026.

The basic forms of activity of social organizations are foundations and associations, which play an important role in supporting the development of local communities' activities for the benefit of their immediate surroundings. According to the list of organizations kept on the industry portal ngo.pl in Zachodniopomorskie (as of March 18, 2024), there are 7,252 non-governmental NGOs, including foundations, registered and ordinary associations, local units of associations with legal personality, physical culture associations, federations, associations of associations, rural housewives' associations. From year to year, the number of these entities is increasing. This proves the increase in the involvement of residents and their readiness to join the implementation of local policies. More voluntary, non-profit, self-governing entities, separate from the local government administration, means a greater variety of services and the actual impact of residents on the quality of life in the commune. The number of associations and foundations is considerable, but many of them operate incidentally (actively function in connection with a specific event), while others deal with a narrow, specific scope of tasks. A small group is actively involved in work for the benefit of the local community, mainly for the development of tourism, the organization of cultural events and support for the disabled (Community-Led Local Development Strategy for 2014-2020 for the Local Action Group „Gryflandia”⁷⁰).

There are a number of different social economy entities operating in Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship (Łukaszuk A. 2009, Best Practices European Social Fund in Zachodniopomorskie 2014). A number of initiatives are undertaken for the development of social economy entities in the region. Organizations are established that support the development of the social economy and involve various entities in cooperation, such as: representatives of public authorities, the non-profit sector, science, social enterprises. Important organizations supporting the social economy in the region are Social Economy Support Centres. The activities undertaken by them in 2020 contributed to the creation of 65 jobs,

⁷⁰ <http://eregion.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/lsr-30.06.2020-r.pdf> Accessed on 10 July 2024

business consulting was provided to 110 entities, 63 animation events were organized, support was provided to 258 entities and 18 training courses, including vocational training, were organized.⁷¹

There are also programs in the field of social assistance and family support aimed at people particularly vulnerable to social exclusion. Examples of such programs are: "Overcome Homelessness. Homeless Assistance Programme", "Meal at school and at home", "From dependence to independence", "Care 75+" Programme, "Programme for the development of care institutions for children up to 3 years of age "toddler", "Respite care", "Care and residential centres".⁷²

The multitude of actions taken at the regional level and the implementation of policies necessary to reduce the vulnerability to social exclusion of the inhabitants of Zachodniopomorskie Voivodeship creates the potential to improve life and build strong local communities.

⁷¹https://es.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/raport_o_stanie_es_w_województwie_zachodniopomorskim_w_2020_r.pdf Accessed on 11 June 2024).

⁷²For more information on these programmes, their assumptions and level of implementation, see: [https://szczecin.uw.gov.pl/systemfiles/articlefiles/17184/\(20230516.175247\).analiza_stanu_i_skuteczności_pomocy_społecznej_w_województwie_zachodniopomorskim_za_2021_rok.pdf](https://szczecin.uw.gov.pl/systemfiles/articlefiles/17184/(20230516.175247).analiza_stanu_i_skuteczności_pomocy_społecznej_w_województwie_zachodniopomorskim_za_2021_rok.pdf) Accessed on 25 August 2024

7. Conclusions and potential focus of MAP Zachodniopomorskie

The area of MAP activity is a place of concentration of many difficult problems, both of a social and economic nature. A significant part of the peripheral areas burdened by the effects of the collapse of state farms is not very attractive for investors, underinvested and largely excluded in terms of transport. Very often the so-called "enclaves of poverty" are formed in these areas. The low level of education of the society in these areas, very often the lack of appropriate qualifications or experience is not conducive to increasing activity on the labour market. Limited access to social, health and educational services excludes young people from social life, who, compared to their peers from cities, have more opportunities to expand their knowledge, competences or skills necessary on the labour market. A significant problem is also limited access to public transport, especially in areas far from city centres, which is not conducive to the continuation of education by young people, as well as not conducive to activity on the labour market. Transport by public transport to the most remote places from the city centres is very often limited to two/three journeys during the day (morning-evening). Public transport does not reach the centre of the village, which results in the need to bring and/or drive children to the bus stop, sometimes more than 2 km from home. Young people who study in cities spend more time commuting and waiting for transport than the time they spend at school. People who require care due to their health condition or disabilities are very often dependent on the help of other family members or the help of neighbours (e.g. shopping for food, medicines, taking to the doctor).

Social economy entities operating in Zachodniopomorskie, including the MAP area, should be considered as important assets of the area, contributing to local development and social inclusion of excluded people. Their role goes beyond ordinary economic activity, including social, integration and activation aspects. The contribution of social economy entities as assets of the area includes activities in the field of:

- professional activation – creating jobs for people at risk of social exclusion, such as the long-term unemployed, people with disabilities and the elderly. Social economy entities create jobs that are often unavailable in the commercial sector, contributing to the reduction of unemployment and the improvement of the financial situation, especially among rural residents,
- provision of social services – providing essential services in rural areas where access to them is limited. These services include care, family support, services for people with disabilities, transport, education and culture, which is essential to meet the needs of residents and improve their quality of life,
- social integration – the activities of social economy entities are based on cooperation and involvement of the local community. The entities contribute to strengthening social capital, trust and activation of residents to act together, which is important in the context of weak social ties in rural areas,

- social innovation – thanks to their bottom-up nature of activity, social economy entities are flexible and able to respond to the specific needs of local communities, proposing innovative solutions, e.g. during the COVID-19 pandemic, social economy entities adapted their activities by offering online services. Social economy actors play an important role in communicating the opportunities for innovative solutions in the areas of organic farming, renewable energy, recycling, sustainable tourism and care services, which contribute to the sustainable development of rural areas,
- strengthening the local economy – social economy entities contribute to the development of local entrepreneurship by offering products and services that can meet local needs. By collaborating with other actors (e.g. business) and creating local networks, they strengthen the local economy, contributing to a more inclusive and resilient society,
- revitalization of rural areas – social economy entities are involved in revitalization projects, revitalizing the local economy and strengthening social ties.

Despite the significant role of social economy entities in local development and counteracting social exclusion in rural areas, their potential is not fully used. The availability of services of reintegration entities is very low, including in particular occupational therapy workshops, social integration centres or social cooperatives. There are mainly foundations and associations in the county. However, they are mostly located in major cities. In 2020, only 11.3% of social service providers were social cooperatives or other social enterprises. This is far below expectations, given the potential of social economy organisations in this area. In addition, the number of occupational therapy workshops does not correspond to the number of occupational activity establishments, which may disturb the natural path of reintegration of people with disabilities.

The creation of rural community centres in rural areas should be assessed positively. They operate in almost all villages of the county. However, what is important, in order to activate the rural community to participate in activities organized in rural community centres, you need a strong leader – a person who will activate the community for joint projects. A leader is a person involved in social life, an initiator of change, someone who helps people shape their environment – without a trusted leader, creating lasting communities and engaging people in grassroots initiatives is difficult. It should be emphasized that leaders need support, but it is not about financial support at all. Rather, it is about mental support - the possibility of integration, development of one's skills, or the acquisition of new skills enabling the management of a group, organization of work, etc. Such support should be provided in particular by local authorities.

The area of operation of the MAP is particularly burdened by the occurrence of long-term unemployment. The highest share in the structure of the unemployed is held by women, young people up to 30 years of age and residents of rural areas. Despite the actions taken by Labour Offices to activate the unemployed, the scale of this phenomenon has been at a high level both at the regional and local level for several years. Therefore, it is necessary to diagnose the basic difficulties that limit their active participation in the labour market and to better "listen" to their needs in order to properly

direct support policy. Previous analyses carried out at the poviast level in the field of assessing the accessibility to public services in the region show that the inhabitants of the Gryfice poviast mostly positively assess access to public administration, social care, pre-school education, primary and secondary education, accessibility to social, sports and recreational infrastructure. On the other hand, they negatively assess the labour market, health care, vocational education, leisure activities for children, youth and seniors, local transport connections or economic activity. This indicates the potential directions MAP activities will focus.

8. Regional overview: Leski-Bieszczadzki region

8.1 Geographic and historical aspects

The Leski-Bieszczadzki MAP region is an area of **2 counties** in the Podkarpackie voivodeship: Leski and Bieszczadzki, which can be shortened together to "Bieszczady" (and this is how we will sometimes refer to the region). The Leski powiat consists of 5 communes: Lesko, Baligród, Cisna, Olszanica, Solina. The Bieszczadzki powiat includes 3 communes: Ustrzyki Dolne, Czarna, Lutowiska. The area is the **border between Poland and Ukraine (European Union border) and Slovakia**. The predominant landscape is mountainous and forested (Western Bieszczady and the largest national park in Poland - Bieszczadzki National Park, Sanocko-Turczańskie Mountains). Both powiats were merged as a result of administrative changes in Poland until 2002 - when they became separate administrative units.

The area of both powiats is predominantly rural, with **two small towns** that are the powiats capitals: Lesko has 5,148 inhabitants and Ustrzyki Dolne has 8,475 (GUS, 2023). In terms of area, Leski **powiat** covers 835 km² and Bieszczadzki **powiat 1,139 km²**. In comparison, Poland is 312,679 km². The MAP area is well below the national average in terms of **urbanisation index** (population living in towns divided by the total population living in the area x 100%): **20% for Leski powiat** and **41% for Bieszczadzki powiat** (2023 data), confirming the rural character of both counties. The average for Poland is 60% (2022).

Figure 8. Location of the region in Poland

Source: Wikipedia. Photo: Katarzyna Gizińska

Table 8. Leski-Bieszczadzki: number of municipalities, area, urbanisation indicator

Specification	Leski powiat	Bieszczadzki powiat	Poland
Number of communes	5	3	2,477 communes (314 poviats, 16 voivodeships)
Area	835 km ²	1,139km ²	312,679 km ²
Urbanisation indicator	20% (2023)	41% (2023)	60% (2022)

Source: GUS, 2023.

The MAP area has had a turbulent history, culminating in the **Second World War** and what followed. However, before we get to the wartime events, it is worth noting that the development of settlement in this area appears in the 14th century during the reign of King Kazimierz The Great and Queen Jadwiga. It is here that **Rusyn highlanders**, or more precisely one of the ethnic groups, called **Boykos** (Bojkwie), began to settle. They specialised in sheep farming in the highlands, grazing cattle in forests and pastures (Nóżka, Scelina, Kozłowski, 2019, p.61).

The border between the Bieszczady Mountains and the Beskid Niski is **the border between the now non-existent ethnographic world of the Lemkos (Łemkowie) and Boykos.**

"Some of them consciously defined themselves as Ukrainians, for many until 1939 national identity was not an important issue. It should also not be forgotten that at that time the region was extremely poor. Most of its inhabitants, regardless of nationality, were illiterate." (Bajda, 2021, p. 36). In addition to the Boykos, the Bieszczady area was also home to the largest

Jewish minority in the region before World War II. They were concentrated in towns - in Ustrzyki Dolne and Lesko, but also in Lutowiska, Baligród or Wola Michowa. Thanks to the Jews, these towns were important trading centres in pre-war times. Poles in the area were a minority and were concentrated in the largest towns. **Gypsies** also lived here, of which there may have been 500 to 600, according to data given in Łukasz Bajda's book. Before the Second World War, three religions mixed here: **Greek Catholicism (about 70%), Roman Catholicism and Judaism.** In the village of Lutowiska, the 'Three Cultures' Ecomuseum was recently created to nurture the memory of the past.

The Second World War was a tragic time: **mass executions** of Jews and Gypsies by the Nazis and resettlement. The **relocations** began during the war – the Soviets resettled the Boykos to the USSR. After the war, during **Operation Vistula in 1947**, Poles resettled the Boykos to the Western and Northern Territories (over 140,000 people!). On the other hand, during the **1951 Operation H-T**, as part of the so-called "correction of the Polish-Soviet border" – there were resettlements of inhabitants to the territory of present-day Ukraine.

It is worth noting that the **San River** flows through both poviats, which during World War II, but also after, was the **demarcation line**, first between the Nazi and Soviet spheres of influence (German-Soviet border) and later, after the war, separating Poland and the USSR (Polish-Soviet border). "Its course was not justified by any historical or ethnic considerations – it turned out to be completely random. The effect of the artificial division was the disintegration of the communities living on both sides of the

border: the breaking of cultural, family and economic ties, as well as the breakdown of church structures: both Roman and Greek Catholic" (Pyżewska, 2020).

With the Second World War and what happened right after it, the once multi-ethnic, **overpopulated Bieszczady Mountains ceased to exist**. What was left were fruit orchards of villages that no longer exist, Jewish cemeteries or Orthodox churches. **After the war, it became a depopulated, rootless area**, which gradually began to be settled, but never returned in numbers to its pre-war population. It is not an easy area to live in – mountains, long winters, transport problems, far from large centres and various types of exclusion. And there remains a living memory of the history of the former inhabitants, e.g. through the art project '**Silent Memorial**'⁷³ by **Arkadiusz Andrejkow**, an artist from Sanok, who decided to paint murals on wooden barns (called descals, from the combination of the word "deska" (Polish "wood"), and "mural"), which are reproductions of old photographs of people who used to live in a given village.

8.2 Demography

The demography of the area changed completely within a few years during World War II and the events just after it. As mentioned, the Bieszczady became depopulated and today is one of the least populated places in Poland. According to data from 2023, there are 25,514 people living in the Leski powiat and 20,702 in the Bieszczadzki powiat. The population density in the Leski powiat is 31 people per km², and in the Bieszczadzki powiat 18 people per km². It is in the Bieszczadzki powiat, which has **the lowest population density of all Polish poviats**, that **the least populated commune in Poland – Lutowiska – 4.5 persons per km²**. In comparison, the average for Poland is 123 persons per km², with approximately 1,074 persons per km² in urban areas and 52 persons per km² in rural areas (GUS 2023).

The share of women in the population is slightly lower than the national average, but women still account for more than half of the population (51%). The feminisation rate is 103 for both poviats, i.e. there are 103 women for every 100 men, and this is lower than the Polish average (107). As mentioned,

⁷³ <https://andrejkow.pl/street-art-cichy-memorial/>

this territory is not an easy place to live. Especially in mountainous areas, strength and stamina are needed to cope with everyday life (e.g. shovelling snow in winter or chopping wood). A second factor that may explain this fact is the historical aspect – when the area was settled after the war, men appeared where there were large tracts of forest – employed in logging or charcoal firing.

In terms of the share of age groups in the population, there are fewer **young people** (under 14) in the Bieszczady than the national average (by 1.5%), in contrast to people aged 15-64. People of this age are more numerous by 2-3 pp. There are also slightly fewer older people (seniors) than the national average, which may show that older people are leaving the area and looking for places closer to larger cities where there is better medical care and access to more services, including care.

The external migration balance (**net international migration**) in both poviats is negative, while the Polish average is positive. In the case of **internal migration**, the balance for the region is also negative, while for Poland it is neutral, showing that more people are permanently leaving than arriving in the Bieszczady. These are data from the end of 2022, i.e. already taking into account the situation of the war in Ukraine, during which many Ukrainians came to Poland. Which shows that for them, the Bieszczady was only a stop on their onward journey, not a destination.

It is worth noting that the average age of an inhabitant of the area is slightly higher than the national average (in the Leski poviat it is slightly higher than in the Bieszczadzki poviat).

The demographic dynamics rate (the ratio of the number of live births to the number of deaths), is **slightly lower than the national average** and is a confirmation of an ageing population: far more people die than are born. In the studied region, the ratio is 0.61 and 0.65, while the average for Poland is 0.68. The fertility rate is also an important factor – lower than the national average. In the Leski poviat it is 1.08 and in the Bieszczadzki poviat it is 1.09, where the Polish average is 1.26. If we would like to maintain the interchangeability of generations, the fertility rate should be at least 2.10 – 2.15.

Table 9. Leski-Bieszczadzki demographic data

Specification	Leski poviat	Bieszczadzki poviat	Poland
Population (2023)	25,514	20,702	37,698,294
% Women	50.7%	50.9%	51.7%
Population density	31 people/ km ²	18 people/ km ²	123 people/km ²
Feminisation rate (how many women per 100 men)	103	103	107
Persons of working age (for men, age group 18-64, for women, 18-59)	61.3%	62.3%	59.2%
Population share of children and young people (<14) ⁷⁴	13.7%	13.7%	15.3%
Share of the population aged 15-65	67.5%	68.8%	65.7%
Share of elderly population (65+)	18.9%	17.5%	19%
Net internal migration (2022)	-57	-102	0

⁷⁴ In Polish statistics, 3 age groups are given: children and adolescents up to 14 years of age, people between 15 and 64 years of age and people 65+. Therefore, we provide data for children up to the age of 14 and not 18, as it was in the template.

Net international migration (2022)	-7	-4	1,939
Average age of population	44 years	42.3 years	42.1 years
Demographic dynamics rate (the ratio of the number of live births to the number of deaths)	0.61	0.65	0.68
Total fertility rate (number of children born to an average woman during the entire childbearing period, 15 - 49 years)	1.08	1.09	1.26

Source: GUS 2022, 2023.

8.3 Economic situation

"In 2021, the national economy recovered from the adverse economic situation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Gross domestic product in real terms in the country increased by almost 7% compared to 2020 and by more than 25% compared to 2015. All regions saw real GDP growth compared to 2020" (Szczygieł 2023, p. 11). The Podkarpackie voivodeship has also seen growth, however, compared to other provinces, it is lagging behind. Looking at GDP per capita, it can be seen that Podkarpackie is lagging strongly behind the national average. In 2021, GDP per capita in Poland was PLN 69,263 (around EUR 16,120), where for Podkarpackie it was PLN 48,544 (around EUR 11,300) and this is the second from the bottom of all 16 voivodeships: **70.1%** of the national average value. The average for Poland in 2021 was PLN 39,986 (around EUR 9,300) and for Podkarpackie it was PLN 31,906 (around EUR 7,400) (79.8% of the average), which is the lowest of all provinces. This shows that **Podkarpackie is a poorer region**. It is developing more and more but is still counted as part of the 'Eastern Bloc' of Poland.

Let us now look in more detail at the MAP area level data we have. We can compare the average salary. An employee in the Leski powiat gets on average PLN 5,831 gross (around EUR 1,360), in the Bieszczadzki powiat PLN 5,747 (around EUR 1,340), and at the same time the national average is PLN 6,705 (around EUR 1,560). This is on average **about 1,000 PLN (around 230 EUR) less than the average Polish salary**. The average gross monthly salary in relation to the national average (Poland=100) in the Leski powiat is 87%, and in the Bieszczadzki powiat 85.7%.

The employment rate is also well below the national average. In the Leski powiat it is 145, in the Bieszczadzki powiat 146, while the Polish average is 259 per 1,000 persons. It is worth taking a look at registered unemployment rates – one can see a huge gap between the studied region and Poland. **Leski powiat has an unemployment rate higher than the average for the whole of Podkarpackie voivodeship, at 19.6%. Bieszczadzki powiat also has a very high unemployment rate – 17.3%, where the national average for the same period is 5.8%**. Looking at the gender breakdown, we can see that **women are more often unemployed than men**, although in the Leski powiat the rate is similar. On the other hand, other statistics show us that among all the employed, women are the majority – in the Leski powiat – 57.9%, in the Bieszczadzki powiat – 57.1%, where the average for the country is 50.3%.

Two comments. When talking to people in the region, it is often claimed that *"here unemployment is only on paper" and "if someone wants to work, they will always find a job"*. On the one hand, the

statistics show a dramatic situation compared to the country, but on the other hand, one does not see this when starting the observation. It is not that unemployment does not exist, but many people are employed in the so-called "grey zone" and some of them do not want to work otherwise because it involves losing benefits and being too much of a liability. A part of people also works seasonally, going, for example, to Germany as a caregiver/caregiver for the elderly.

"I would like to employ my employees on normal contracts, well of course I would. But these people don't want to. Do you know why? It's because they're usually women and they're often looking after their elderly mother, father-in-law or someone else in the family. And first of all, they receive benefits for this work, social benefits. So, by working for me, they will officially lose this benefit. And secondly – working on a contract is a big commitment that limits them. And they say they want to work, but when they get a call from home that something is going on, they have to go out and there is no working from 8 a.m. to 4 p.m. For them, work is important, it gives them money, but family and family commitments are more important. Here you live a really traditional life. Here, no one puts an elderly person in a care home. Because it's not appropriate. But there are no places like that either."

The second observation concerns an apparent contradiction – on the one hand, women are more often unemployed, while on the other hand, among all those in work, they are the majority. This is due to the fact that women are more likely to register officially as unemployed at labour offices than men.

The main economic sectors are agriculture, forestry services and tourism. It is worth noting that there is no large industry in the area, no large employer that can employ hundreds or thousands of people. The majority of entrepreneurs are **micro-entrepreneurs** with 0 to 9 employees, and they are the ones pulling the local economy forward. What is also typical is the **seasonality of work**. In some places the tourist season is from May to October, but there are also places where winter tourism is booming, such as in the Olszanica or Ustrzyki Dolne municipalities.

If you talk to people, you will see that **often one person does more than one thing**, especially in the more touristic areas. For example, he or she runs his or her own small business (renting out a cottage, running a yoga class or other type of service), but also works in an office or acts as a counsellor. One person, especially when it comes to the more active individuals, has different social and professional roles. During the MAP meeting, it was very difficult for MAP members to identify which stakeholder group they belonged to, because, for example, someone was a university lecturer until recently, at the same time is a municipal authority, is involved in social activities within the NGO.

If we look at the issues of innovation and valuable resources that can lift this region up, then, apart from various initiatives related to the **development of tourism** (e.g. the longest Tyrolean in Poland, the longest tubing track in the world, ski slopes or ski-tour trails), it is worth mentioning the recently established **Solina Renewable Energy Cluster (Soliński Klaster Eneгии)** – the second energy cluster after the South-Western Energy Cluster, of which PGE Energia Odnawialna S.A. (*the largest energy holding company operating on the Polish market and one of the largest entities of its kind in Central and Eastern Europe*) is the Founding Partner. Established on 17 February 2018, the Solina Renewable Energy Cluster covers the powiat of Lesko with its scope. The development of the idea of energy clusters leads to stable energy supply and self-sufficiency of energy at the commune or powiat level. The project takes

into account the local specificity and the need to activate the development of the region through the use of locally available energy resources, above all renewable energy sources. The signatories of the agreement on the establishment of the Solina Energy Cluster are: Leski Poviát, Solina Commune, Elbest sp. z o.o. and PGE Energia Odnawialna S.A.”⁷⁵ It is worth mentioning that the **Baligród Renewable Energy Cluster** has also been established in the MAP area.

Table 10. Leski-Bieszczadzki: economic indicators of the region

Specification	Leski powiat	Bieszczadzkipowiat	Poland
GDP / capita (2021)	48,544 PLN (data for Podkarpackie voivodeship)		69,263 PLN
Gross disposable income in household sector (2021)	31,906 PLN (data for Podkarpackie voivodeship)		39,986 PLN
Employment rate (per 1,000 persons) (2021)	145	146	259
Women among all employees (2021)	57.9%	57.1%	50.3%
Registered unemployment (2021)	19.6%	17.3%	5.8%
Unemployment rate Women / Men (from 2021)	19.7% / 19.5%	19.7% / 15.2%	6.6% / 5.1%
Average gross salary (2022)	5,831 PLN	5,747 PLN	6,705 PLN
Average gross monthly wages and salaries in relation to the national average (Poland=100)	87.0%	85.7 %	
Main economic sectors (2021)	7.4% agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing, 19.3% industry and construction 73.3% other activities	27.7% agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing) 13.1% industry and construction 17.3% services 2.3% work in the financial sector	10.3% (agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing), 30.1% industry and construction 23.4% services 3.6% work in the financial sector

Source: GUS, 2021, 2022, 2023.

8.4 Institutional setting

Before going into the statistics, it is clear from talking to residents in both poviats that they perceive the MAP area as a place where there is limited access to services, education and healthcare. Therefore, they often travel outside the area – for example to see **specialist doctors**. There is no university level college in the MAP area. Therefore, young people who want to study at a university or polytechnic, choose universities in the Regional capital or further away. The **lack of organised care for young children** is also a problem in the region (e.g. in the typical mountain municipalities there is often no nursery and insufficient kindergarten places). There are primary schools in each commune, however, secondary schools are not everywhere. These are concentrated in the powiat capitals, which is a problem for children from, for example, the municipalities of Cisna or Lutowiska – because **the distance from the place of residence to the secondary school can be about 50-60 km** and it is impossible to get to school every day, especially as there is no public transport in these most remote

⁷⁵ Read more: <https://pgeeo.pl/aktualnosci/solinski-klaster-energii-z-certyfikatem-pilotazowego-klastera-energii>, <https://pgeeo.pl/aktualnosci/w-solinie-powstanie-klaster-energii.-jednym-z-inwestorow-bedzie-pge-energia-odnawialna>

areas. Children of secondary school age therefore start to use boarding schools and leave their family homes at the age of 15. They only return for weekends.

People living in the region, especially in the more distant parts, which are typically rural, complain about the **lack of good access to healthcare**. Often there is also no **pharmacy/pharmacy point** where one can buy medicines and one has to drive sometimes even many kilometres. This is a problem for the elderly and non-motorised people. One type of facilitation is **medical advice by telephone**, which have become widespread due to the Covid-19 pandemic. **For example, in the Bieszczadzki powiat, out of 130,000 outpatient consultations in 2023, almost 15,000 were by telephone** (Local Data Bank, 2023). Thus, more than **10% of the services provided** in health care were provided **without the need to travel**.

The further away from the powiat towns, the less access to services there is. In very small villages, residents **do not have a shop** and have to have **their own means of transport** and drive several kilometres to get basic necessities. Shops, post office, bank, car mechanic. In many villages **there are no ATMs, no gas stations**. Grocery shops often serve as multi-branch shops and, in high season, as souvenir shops. It is characteristic of the area that **services are combined at one point**, just as one person performs several social roles and sometimes has several different types of jobs.

There are **3 nurseries** in the MAP area, **only in the cities**, so those living outside the city do not have the possibility to send their children to them. As far as pre-schoolers are concerned, there are a total of one and a half thousand children in pre-school facilities, but it should be noted that in these smaller towns the distance to pre-school can be considerable, which is a handicap for parents. **School buses take children to school, but not to kindergartens**, so the burden of transport falls on the parents. Therefore, we see that the **percentage of children in pre-school education here is lower than the national average**. For the Leski powiat it is 81.8%, for the Bieszczadzki powiat 89%, and the average for Poland is 92.7% (Local Data Bank, 2022).

There are 29 elementary schools in the MAP area and the **enrolment rate for children aged 7-14 is 86.67 in the Leski powiat and 88.45 in the Bieszczadzki powiat**. These values are below the national average, which is 95.96% (Local Data Bank, 2022). As far as secondary schools are concerned, children can choose 5 schools in the Leski powiat– 1 high school, 1 trade school and 3 technical schools. There are also 5 schools in the Bieszczadzki powiat: 2 high schools, 2 trade schools and 1 technical school. As for students, there is a lack of data at the regional level – this is due to the fact that children mainly pursue their higher education outside the MAP area.

In terms of healthcare provision, the MAP area is served by two hospitals located in the powiat towns. What is noteworthy is that **there is an obstetrics ward in only one of them. In Ustrzyki Dolne, the gynaecology-obstetrics department was recently closed**. This is a disadvantage for women in the region, and even more so in mountainous areas, because, for example, it is 60 km from Dwernik to the hospital in Lesko, which is about 1 hour in summer, but can be much longer in winter. **Statistically, there are more beds available in the MAP area than the national average**. In the Leski powiat it is as many as **71 beds per 10,000 inhabitants, where the national average is 44** (Local Data Bank, 2022). However, it must be added that these beds are also used by people who come to the area on a short-

term basis. In terms of the **number of healthcare clinics**, the MAP area is in line with the national average, with 6 clinics per 10,000 inhabitants. **While the number of beds is surprising and the number of clinics is not far from the national average, the number of doctors is worse. There are 17 doctors per 10,000 inhabitants in the Leski powiat and 23 in the Bieszczadzki powiat, while the national average is 34** (Local Data Bank, 2022). In terms of pharmacies, the **Leski powiat** is close to the national average, with **1 pharmacy per less than 3 thousand people. In the Bieszczadzki powiat, 1 pharmacy is per approximately 3,500 people** (Local Data Bank, 2022). These statistics do not take into account **tourists, who number several hundred thousand people per year in the Bieszczady National Park alone**. Help is provided by over-the-counter first-aid medicines, which can be bought in shops or at gas stations.

Access to culture seems difficult at first sight. However, the statistics here are quite optimistic. The MAP area stands out above the average when it comes to the number of people per 1 cultural institution or library. There are 7 libraries and 2 cultural institutions per 10 thousand inhabitants in the Leski powiat, and 3 libraries and almost 2 cultural institutions in the Bieszczadzki powiat. The average for the country is: 2 libraries and 1 cultural institution (Local Data Bank, 2022 and 2023). But it should be noted that these **positive figures do not reflect the reality, which is the considerable distances that have to be travelled to get to the cultural centre and library**. That is why, for example, the commune of Ustrzyki Dolne has started to implement a very interesting idea of a **Mobile Library, the so-called Bibliobus**.

Figure 9. Photo of Bibliobus

Source: FB Gmina Ustrzyki Dolne / <https://www.facebook.com/gminaUstrzykiDolne>

The MAP area is a peripheral region, far from the centre, and as a result, there are various problematic issues related to the mobility of residents. Until recently, the problem was the **state of the roads**. There

has been quite a change in recent years. The so-called "Great Bieszczady Loop", i.e. the road which surrounds both poviats and is the main transit and access road, has been renovated. Many smaller streets were also renovated, such as the one from Zatwarnica to Dwernik, one of the roads "at the end of the world", because it ended in Zatwarnica and then there are only mountains, so it was not treated as a priority investment. Completing the historical outline, Zatwarnica used to be one of the larger villages in the region, an economic centre and the seat of the commune, with a population of 1,056 and 148 houses in 1931. In May 1946, the entire village was displaced to the USSR (Mielnikiewicz 2024). Currently, 198 people are registered in the village. This is a typical story of many Bieszczady villages, which now have few inhabitants and thus have to struggle to make their voices heard against the many other needs of the commune. The local government weighs up the rationale because the commune's budget is not made of rubber. There are many such roads "at the end of the world" that are waiting for their turn. They are not reached by buses, or if they are reached, they are unable to meet the needs of the residents.

It is difficult to cite any statistics as they are not collected at poviat level. The only indicator is the number of cars per 1,000 inhabitants. It is not surprising that the inhabitants of the MAP area have more cars than the Polish average **of 700 cars, for the Leski poviat it is 795, and for the Bieszczadzki poviat - 895 (GUS 2022)**. The lack of a car makes it impossible to reach many places, as **public transport is insufficient. Residents of this area need a minimum of 2 hours** (and from more distant areas, about 3) to reach Rzeszów and **there is no more distant region in the entire voivodeship than the MAP area** (MROW 2022).

As far as services are concerned, there are **problems with mobile phone coverage** in the MAP area, especially in the mountainous areas, **and thus with internet**. Therefore, remote work can be problematic.

8.5 Policies/instruments/initiatives – local-rural development

The **rural development initiative** in the MAP area is mainly **implemented** by 2 associations:

1. **Local Action Group "Zielone Bieszczady"**⁷⁶ based in **Orelec**, area of activity of the municipalities: Lutowiska, Czarna, Ustrzyki Dolne, Olszanica, Solina, Sanok (rural commune) and Tyrawa Wołoska,
2. **Local Action Group "Nasze Bieszczady"**⁷⁷ based in **Lesko**, area of action of the municipalities: Baligród, Cisna, Komańcza, Lesko and Zagórz.

They are currently implementing the **Rural Development Programme 2014-2020** (perspective extended to September 2024) providing support to candidates for entrepreneurs, existing companies for development, they also support communes and NGOs, promote local services and products, local heritage and build and modernise non-commercial, generally accessible tourist, recreational

⁷⁶ <https://www.lgd-zielonebieszczady.pl>

⁷⁷ <http://www.nasze-bieszczady.pl>

infrastructure for inhabitants and tourists visiting the Bieszczady. They support initiatives that improve the lives of the inhabitants of these rural areas. The **two tri-sectoral associations** (public, economic and social sectors) signed on 1st September 2024 agreements to implement new two-fund **Local Development Strategies** this time for the next financial perspective.

Both the past financial perspective (RDP 2007-2013), the ongoing one (RDP 2014-2020) and the new one (**Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027** and **European Funds for Podkarpackie 2021-2027**) **do not cover the needs of the area**. The cross-border location indicated in the report, poor accessibility in terms of communication, services, health care or education **can only to a small extent be met by the LEADER initiative** funds. Especially as the **funding depends on the number of inhabitants, which is not a favourable criterion as the statistics for the MAP area show**.

It is worth noting that social initiatives in these rural areas are also supported by other institutions/programmes with much smaller budgets, such as:

- "Act Locally" programme–Bieszczady Foundation, II. "Carpathian Local Initiatives"– Association for the Development and Promotion of Podkarpacie "Pro Carpathia", or III. "Podkarpackie Local Initiatives"– Local Space Foundation. Bieszczady Foundation (Fundacja Bieszczadzka) in cooperation with the Academy for the Development of Philanthropy in Poland announce the annual Local Grant Competition in the framework of the 'Act Locally' Programme of the Polish-American Freedom Foundation. The programme is addressed to non-governmental organisations and informal groups, which make a joint effort to make life in their community better, work for the common good.

In 2024: applications could be submitted by Applicants operating in 10 municipalities: Baligród, Bircza, Czarna, Komańcza, Lesko, Lutowska, Olszanica, Solina, Tyrawa Wołoska, Ustrzyki Dolne. It was possible to apply for a grant of up to PLN 6,000 own contribution - 25% of the value of the grant applied for, including a 5% financial contribution.⁷⁸

- "Carpathian Local Initiatives" (Karpackie Inicjatywy Lokalne): The 'Pro Carpathia' Association held a competition for Carpathian local initiatives within the framework of the task entitled 'Carpathian local initiatives' funded by the National Institute of Freedom - Centre for Civil Society Development within the framework of the Governmental Programme Civic Initiatives Fund NOWEFIO for 2021-2030. The aim of the competition was to increase the involvement of young organisations and informal groups in public life through the implementation of local Carpathian initiatives related to the promotion of the cultural and natural heritage of the Polish part of the Carpathian region (Śląskie, Małopolskie and Podkarpackie voivodeships). The initiatives implemented have contributed to: maintaining national tradition, development of national and civic awareness, increasing civic activity among e.g. young people, seniors, promoting pro-environmental basics among project recipients.

The following could apply for grants: young non-governmental organisations, informal groups

⁷⁸ <https://fundacijabieszczadzka.org/dzialaj-lokalnie/>

(independent or under a patron). The maximum grant amount is PLN 10,000 gross, but not less than PLN 3,000.⁷⁹

- Podkarpackie Local Initiatives" (Podkarpackie Inicjatywy Lokalne, PIL) - a support for community initiatives and young organisations: 'Podkarpackie Local Initiatives 2024-2026 - edition 2024' is a Project co-financed from the funds of the National Institute of Freedom - Centre for Civil Society Development within the framework of the "Government Programme Civic Initiatives Fund NOWEFIO for 2021-2030". The project operator is the Local Space Foundation, the LAG Association 'Partnership for the Nizańskie Land' and the LAG 'Trygon-Development and Innovation'.

The objective of the measure is to strengthen and increase the institutional development of non-governmental organisations and provide opportunities for the implementation of initiatives to organisations and informal groups operating in the Podkarpackie voivodeship. Within the project there are calls for proposals for the whole voivodeship, which enable support for initiatives undertaken by various informal groups (depending on the chosen path, funding of up to PLN 6,000) and young non-governmental organisations, which have been registered in the National Court Register or the relevant register not earlier than 60 months before the day of submitting the application for micro-grant, and its annual income for the previous completed financial year did not exceed PLN 50,000 (co-financing under the 'Organisation Development Plan' up to PLN 10,000). The project also envisages animation and educational activities aimed at the development and professionalisation of non-governmental organisations in our voivodeship.

The recipients of the planned activities are the inhabitants of Podkarpackie voivodeship, to whom the initiative implemented by the beneficiaries of the task is addressed. The project makes it possible to benefit from consulting and training support, and to participate in seminars on how to implement and monitor actions taken.⁸⁰

8.6 Policies/instruments/initiatives - supporting the social economy and/or social enterprises

Support for entrepreneurs and the social economy is guaranteed by the regional programme – **European Funds for Podkarpackie 2021-2027**. It is worth pointing out here **direct grants from the European Regional Development Fund** under the regional programme European Funds for Podkarpackie 2021-2027 (1.3 SME support - Grant, Project type: Support for the development and competitiveness of SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises) in the form of a grant). Support is dedicated to entrepreneurs based in 1 of the 43 border municipalities (including the MAP area) to SMEs in the field of investment projects, including, inter alia, production investments, consisting in increasing the production capacity, extension of plants, diversification of products/services, changes

⁷⁹ <https://www.procarpathia.pl/projekty/projekty-krajowe/karpackie-inicjatywy-lokalne>

⁸⁰ www.podkarpackieinicjatywylokalne.pl

in the way of production/services provision, which lead to an increase in the development and competitiveness of SMEs both in the regional, national and international markets.

Support for social enterprises in the area of MAP is offered, among others, by the **Podkarpacka Agencja Konsultingowo-Doradcza, based in Jasło, implementing the project "Podkarpacki Ośrodek Wspierania Ekonomii Społecznej III" (POWES = Podkarpackie Social Economy Support Centre)**, which is co-financed from the European Social Fund Plus under Priority No. FEPK.07 "Human capital ready for changes" of the regional programme European Funds for Podkarpackie 2021-2027. The area of project implementation: 3 sub-regions of the Podkarpackie Voivodeship, i.e. poviats: jasielski, krośnieński, M. Krosno, brzozowski, sanocki, leski and bieszczadzki. The project is aimed at individuals and social economy entities (including social enterprises) and offers support: animation, training, counselling, incubation, financial and business support as a response to diagnosed problems and barriers.

9. Vulnerability and social exclusion in the Leski-Bieszczadzki region

9.1 Social exclusion and poverty

According to the Statistics Poland (GUS) report on poverty in 2022 "the extent of economic poverty in total households in Poland remained at a similar level as in 2021, although the average material situation of households worsened in real terms, among other reasons due to high inflation. As in the previous year, the extreme poverty rate was less than 5%, the relative poverty rate around 12% and the statutory poverty rate around 7%."

Figure 10. Poverty incidence in Poland between 2010 and 2022 according to the poverty lines adopted in a given year (% of persons in households)

Source:

https://stat.gov.pl/files/gfx/portalinformacyjny/pl/defaultaktualnosci/5487/14/10/1/zasieg_ubostwa_ekonomicznego_w_polsce_w_2022_roku.pdf

The report goes on to say that 'those most at risk of extreme poverty in 2022 included people from households living mainly from non-earned sources other than pensions (about 12%), as well as households of **farmers** (8.5%) and **pensioners** (about 6%). **The group least at risk of extreme poverty were people from households whose main source of income was self-employment** (about 3%). Lower extreme poverty rates than the national average were also observed among households of pensioners (4%) and employees (4.5%). In 2022, the level of education also strongly differentiated the extent of extreme poverty. It can be said that **with increasing levels of education, the extent of extreme poverty decreased.**" Among the factors that influence the risk of poverty, the report identifies, in addition to **livelihoods and education level: the number of children in the household, age, disability, place of residence (rural).**

Podkarpackie voivodeship (where the MAP area is located) is one of the voivodeships with **an increased poverty risk. The average for Poland is 13.7%, and for Podkarpackie 17.4%**. The result is not the highest – it is found in the Podlaskie voivodeship (23.4%), while the lowest is 7.8% – in the Dolnośląskie voivodeship. This can also be seen in other indicators: average monthly disposable income and average monthly expenditure per person in the household. These values are lower than the national average. Podkarpackie voivodeship has **the lowest average monthly disposable income per person in households in relation to the national average - 81.3%**, which translates into PLN 1,829 (around EUR 425) (the national average is PLN 2,688, i.e., around EUR 625).

Another indicator that shows the economically weaker situation of the inhabitants of the MAP area is the **data on social assistance**. In both poviats the share of population benefiting from community social assistance due to low incomes are above the national average, which is 3.4%, while 3.9% in the Leski poviats and 5.3% in the Bieszczadzki poviats. In terms of the number of beneficiaries of community social assistance per 10 thousand people, the national average is 344 people, in the Leski – 388, and in the Bieszczadzki – 529. Although relatively more people benefit from social assistance in the MAP area, this is not matched by the number of facilities that provide assistance, such as day care centres. It is worth noting that **in the Bieszczadzki poviats there were two such facilities in 2022, and now there are none**. Likewise with the birthing centre – it was closed recently.

Table 11. Leski-Bieszczadzki: Social assistance indicators

Specification	Leski poviats	Bieszczadzki poviats	Poland
Average monthly disposable income per person in the household	1,829.05 PLN (for Podkarpackie voivodeship)		2,249.79 PLN
Average monthly expenses per person in the household	1,162.28 PLN (for Podkarpackie voivodeship)		1,475.22 PLN
Poverty risk indicator	17.4 %		13.7%
Beneficiaries of community social assistance per 10,000 population	388	529	344
Social welfare coverage by income criterion and economic age groups	3.9%	5.3%	3.4%
Total number of daytime support centres	2 (2022). 0 (2023)	1	3,003
Residential community care centres	1 (2022). 2 (2023)	1	2,127
Families to whom aid was granted on the basis of a decision by reasons (Dimensions: Reasons for granting aid - poverty)	291	283	339,266

Source: GUS, 2022.

9.2 Labour market

Residents of the region have considerably less access jobs. However, it should be taken into account that, although there is less choice, according to MAP members, there is work – but this is for seasonal work, especially in tourism. This is often associated with instability of employment, working without a contract or under civil law contracts or not paying health and/or social security contributions.

The MAP area is the region where there are **more long-term unemployed (over 1 year) than the national average and these are mostly women**. There is also a **much higher rate of registered unemployed people who have been unemployed for more than 1 year**: in the Leski powiat 5.7%, Bieszczadzki powiat 4.3%, where the national average is 1.5%.

One of the determinants of registered unemployment is the **level of education**. Persons with **basic/vocational education constitute the largest group of unemployed**. "The 2021 census data showed that **the higher the level of education, the higher the percentage of employed and the lower the percentage of economically inactive in both rural and urban areas**. Differences in economic activity status between those living in urban and rural areas are evident for each level of education. In 2021, there was a higher proportion of employed in rural areas than in urban areas and a lower proportion of economically inactive. There was a higher proportion of unemployed in the city than in the countryside among those with basic vocational and lower secondary education or less. The proportion of unemployed with tertiary education among both urban and rural residents was relatively small" (GUS 2024 – Population on the labour market, p.30). This type of regularity is also observed in the MAP area. It is worth adding that, **according to the latest data (Q1 2024), in Podkarpackie voivodeship the largest number of unemployed are people aged 35 to 44, and the smallest group among the unemployed are those aged 18 to 24**.

However, **statistics do not fully reflect the real situation**, they do not talk about the "grey zone", seasonal work, casual work (e.g. among young people), work on civil law contracts, work abroad. Interviews with MAP members show that some people who work in tourism during the season go abroad to work in the off-season, e.g. to care for the elderly in Germany.

Therefore, the situation on the Bieszczady labour market cannot be fully assessed through statistics alone. The question about the level of education is important, but it is important to point out something that is characteristic not only for this area, but also for tourist destinations. **That some of the people who live here are not registered here**. Sometimes they come for a while, sometimes for a few years, and sometimes they put down roots and register (or not). These are often visitors from larger cities. MAP members say that they are often educated people, usually middle-aged, who either work remotely or dream of living here and have a business idea. There are no statistics available on this group of people.

It is worth recalling here the emerging division into **3 groups of inhabitants in the MAP area**:

1. **birds** - new residents who have recently 'flown in' and it is not known whether they will fly away quickly
2. **bushes** - residents who have been living here for a while but have not yet put down roots
3. **trunks** - residents who feel 'from here', who have their roots here

The MAP area is unique in that few people can say 'trunk' about themselves, while most are 'bush' or 'bird' (Gizińska, 2022).

When it comes to the phenomenon defined as NEET, i.e. young people (**15-24 years old**) who are not in work, education or training, there is no local data that could be directly related to this topic – but there are data at the voivodeship level and trends that are typical for the whole country. "In 2022, the percentage of people not showing any of the three mentioned activities [education, vocational training, work] **was 10.3% in Podkarpackie voivodeship, one of the highest in the country (with a national average of 8.0%)**. Only in Warmińsko-Mazurskie Voivodeship was its level higher – 10.8%. The lowest level of this indicator was recorded in Wielkopolskie (5.5%) and Śląskie (7.0%) voivodeships (In the case of Lubuskie, Opolskie, Świętokrzyskie and Podlaskie voivodeships, data on the amount of the NEET indicator in 2022 is not available). **The value of the NEET indicator recorded in Podkarpackie voivodeship in 2022 was lower than in 2021 by 3.1 percentage points** (nationally, the value of the NEET indicator in 2022 was lower by 3.2 p.p. in relation to 2021). The NEET rate is also calculated for the wider age group of **15-29 years**. In this age group, **it was 15.0% in Podkarpackie voivodeship in 2022 (and 17.1% in 2021)**. **In Poland, the respective values are 10.9% (2022) and 13.4% (2021)**. The indicator in Podkarpackie voivodeship was **the highest among all voivodeships**.⁸¹" (Mazurkiewicz 2021, p. 5).

It is worth adding that **self-employment** is popular for the MAP area. These are **the highest rates compared to the whole province!** (Fig. 12). According to the latest data from the Statistical Office in Rzeszów, the **average for Poland is 98 persons per 1,000, for the Podkarpackie voivodeship 76 (!), and for the MAP area the figures are above 100 (!!!!)**. Running a business is a kind of taking matters into own hands, being own boss, knowing the basics of law and accounting (or having a good accountant), it is "being on your own".

⁸¹ Based on: <https://rot.podkarpackie.pl/2-1-edukacja?highlight=WyJuZWV0II0=>

Figure 12. Employment indicators of the region

Mapa 4. Osoby fizyczne prowadzące działalność gospodarczą – kwiecień 2024 r.
Map 4. Natural persons conducting economic activity – April 2024

Source: https://rot.podkarpackie.pl/images/baza_wiedzy/Komunikaty/Powiaty/komunikat_kwiecień_2024.pdf

Table 12. Unemployment

Specification	Leski powiat	Bieszczadzki powiat	Poland
Registered unemployment (2021)	19.6%	17.3%	5,8%
Registered unemployment longer than 1 year - total as % of total unemployed (2022)	49.9%	48.9%	40,5%
Registered unemployment longer than 1 year - women as % of unemployed women (2022)	50.1%	55.5%	43,3%
Registered unemployment for more than 1 year - unemployed as % of working age population (2022)	5.7%	4.3%	1,5%
Unemployed people by education level (GUS April 2024)	Higher education - 10.8% Post-secondary vocational and secondary vocational - 30.9% General secondary school - 9.5% Basic vocational - 28.7%	Higher education - 10.7% Post-secondary vocational and secondary vocational - 24.3% General secondary school - 11.6% Basic vocational - 28.7%	Higher education - 14.5% Post-secondary vocational and secondary vocational - 22.2% General secondary school - 12.5% Basic vocational education - 24.6%

	Lower secondary. primary. incomplete primary - 20.2%	Lower secondary. primary. incomplete secondary education - 24.8%	Lower secondary, primary, incomplete secondary education - 26.3%
NEET indicator (15-24) (ROT 2022)	10.3% (for Podkarpackie voivodeship)		8%
NEET indicator (15-29) (ROT 2022)	15% (for Podkarpackie voivodeship)		10.9%

Source: GUS, 2022, 2024; Podkarpackie Regionalne Obserwatorium Terytorialne (ROT) 2022.

There are various factors that influence vulnerability. In the MAP area, most of the socio-economic factors are present and relevant. However, what comes to the fore is the **peripherality of the area**. This is associated with limited opportunities on many levels - limited educational opportunities, limited labour market and lower wages, limited services including health care, lack of care for the elderly or disabled, lack of organised care for the smallest children. This also contributes to the brain drain.

Another factor is the **low population density**, which is linked to social and communication exclusion, to the difficulty of integrating residents who are dispersed. Add to this the older age of the inhabitants, the problems of shuttling or the lack of a car. Moreover, it means lower revenues of communes' budgets, because there are few residents paying PIT in the MAP area.

Talking to MAP members also reveals a factor that is often in the background, that becomes almost transparent and hard to see, but it is there. It is not crucial, but it is worth mentioning because on the one hand it is present, but on the other hand it is a bit of a taboo subject – **alcohol abuse**. Alcoholism is more an effect of living in this area than a cause, but it does create a vicious circle and excludes people who find themselves in an alcohol crisis. It is worth mentioning the activities of the "Lucky-Ski" Foundation, which also includes people from this group in its activities.

It is interesting to note that the situation across the eastern border and the outbreak of **war in Ukraine**, which borders the Bieszczady powiat, is not a significant factor in the vulnerability of the inhabitants of the MAP area. Naturally, the war in Ukraine caused fear, anxiety, uncertainty about the future – but this was typical for the whole of Poland, not just the border areas.

9.3 Disadvantaged groups

There are different groups at risk of exclusion in the MAP area. In the preparatory phase of the project, the following groups were defined: women, older people and migrants. However, in the course of the research and interviews with MAP members, two other groups also came to the surface: people with disabilities and young people. Migrants, on the other hand, were identified as a group that is not excluded because, after the first wave of refugees from Ukraine, it became clear that there are not many migrants, and two, there is systemic state care and widespread assistance targeted at Ukrainians.

One of the main factors that cause exclusion is the woman's role as mother and caretaker of the household. In the MAP area, more conservative attitudes and expectations regarding social roles can be observed. By staying at home with the children, taking care of the household and caring for the elderly in their family or their husband's family, women become more socially and economically

excluded. Often, for this reason, they do not take up registered work that would result in the setting aside pension contributions, to secure their future in post-working age. Women in Poland, as is also very evident in the MAP area, are able to support each other in the daily hardships of life in rural areas in the form of Rural **Housewives' Circles** (Rural Housewives' Circles in Poland are a voluntary, self-governing and independent socio-professional women's organisations operating mainly in rural areas). Currently, there are as many as 50 circles registered in the MAP area, thanks to which women integrate, work together for the benefit of the local community, but also improve their competencies, train and carry out economic activities, e.g. in the form of selling food products, handicrafts, homemade liquors or services. The circles also provide access to culture, e.g. by organising trips to the theatre or concerts.

Older people are excluded largely in terms of transport, but also economically. If they have mobility problems and do not have someone close by who can take them to the doctor, to a neighbour, to the village hall, to church or to neighbourhood meetings – they become socially excluded. Added to this is the issue of the level of pensions they receive, which for many people is insufficient to meet their living and health needs. Older people are also digitally excluded. It is worth recalling here the programme implemented by the Local Action Group "Zielone Bieszczady" – the project "THE CHANCE" (SZANSA) – new opportunities for adults" from the Operational Programme Knowledge Education Development 2014-2020⁸². The project is targeting the development of digital and social competences implemented in a group format. What is very important, the project provided for the transportation of participants to the training site. This two-year project coincided perfectly with the pandemic, as it gave seniors the chance to familiarise themselves with new technologies and allowed them to interact with others. It reduced digital exclusion and helped to maintain intergenerational links (the project involved young people). It also showed how crucial it is to take care of the logistics.

It is worth mentioning that active senior citizens integrate through the **Retirees' Circle**, but not everyone participates. They also start **Third Age Universities** themselves or with the help of communes or NGOs, which are booming in Poland. In the MAP area there is the Ustrzyki University of the Third Age, run by the Ustrzyki Cultural Association and under the honorary patronage of the Mayor of Ustrzyki Dolne.⁸³

Young people came up in conversations with MAP members, who say that there are no prospects for young people here, no opportunities for development, so they are not surprised that young people want to flee. Young people do not have access to what their peers in the cities have access to (opportunities to pursue unusual passions, education, leisure activities – the topic of the lack of gyms, for example, came up). At the age of 15, young people often leave their family homes and go to boarding schools, especially those from more mountainous areas, as the distance to secondary schools is long (up to 50-60 km) and there is no daily commute. Exclusion of young people takes the form of exclusion from cultural life - there is a lack of youth-oriented offers and infrastructure. There is also a

⁸² <https://szansa.lgd-zielonebieszczady.pl>

⁸³ For more information: https://ustrzyki-dolne.pl/aktualnosc-7015-ruszaja_zapisy_na_kolejny_rok.html.

lack of peers. And in addition, due to the small population and lack of public transport, young people are also excluded by transport, so they have limited opportunities to participate in social life. As part of the activities of the Lucky-Ski Foundation, a small, backyard gym has been launched, which can be used by residents and wards of the foundation. It is a meeting place for young people

People with disabilities were added at the very end, after MAP members met and talked about exclusion. Both people with disabilities and their families are at risk of exclusion. Disability is still a taboo subject – it is almost invisible in the public space, not much is said about it. Exclusion is a result of a lack of appropriate day care places, but also 24-hour care, a lack of appropriate activities, a lack of infrastructure and a systemic lack of support. The biggest problem is with people who are entering adulthood - there are no prospects for them, no job opportunities, no inclusion in various activities, no Professional Activity Facility (Zakład Aktywności Zawodowej, ZAZ). In the commune of Olszanica, until last year, there was a Social Integration Centre – it was a unique facility, which gave the opportunity to include excluded people, including those with disabilities. By a resolution of the Olszanica Commune Council, the facility ceased to exist.

9.4 Access to services

There is **a fair amount of social activity among residents** in the MAP area. From conversations with MAP members, it seems that it is precisely in places where it is more difficult, where there are not so many resources, where it is far to the nearest neighbour – that many different grassroots initiatives arise, which show that **if the state does not reach out with help, nor the local government, there is another way – people can help themselves and become more of a civil society**. This is demonstrated, for example, by the activity of the **Association of Bieszczady Initiatives "Przełączenie" ["Switching"] from Dwernik**, which was established in 2021 and "is the fruit of a joint initiative of inhabitants and enthusiasts of the Bieszczady Mountains, experienced professionals from various fields, such as tourism, self-governance or financial consultancy. Our organization brings together people who not only love these picturesque areas, but also have a wealth of experience in areas important for the development of the region"⁸⁴. The association leased a neglected area in Dwernik on the San River from the Lutowska commune and prepared it as a tent base with its own efforts, building a shelter, a pizza oven and a bread oven. In addition, we have hammocks between the trees and a beach by the San River. Funding for statutory activity is based on, among other things, the fees from running the tent base, which enable it to raise funds for its statutory activities and its mission, i.e. initiating activities for the comprehensive and sustainable development of the local community.

The MAP area shows a high level of activity of social organisations and Rural Housewives' Circles (RHCs). Out of 14,340 RHCs registered in Poland, as many as 50 fall in this small, so sparsely populated fragment of Poland! Out of 37,000 registered foundations, 61 are active in the MAP area, whereas 297 out of a total of 135,000 registered associations and social organisations in Poland, are active in the MAP area. When one observes internet forums, Facebook, and talks to people, the topic of

⁸⁴ <https://www.bieszczadzka.org>

associations, foundations, or activities of RHCs comes up again and again – e.g. a RHC organised a festival, a foundation organised a marathon, or an association organised neighbourhood meetings.

Community organisations also run businesses, which is noteworthy because this way of earning money is sometimes part of the social economy and they are the ones who partially run social enterprises in the MAP area. And they offer services that are lacking in the MAP area, targeting excluded people, e.g. children with disabilities (the "Lucky Ski" Foundation or the Bieszczady Association "Promyk Nadziei") or including excluded people in the labour market (Bieszczady Sp. z o. o. social enterprise). This shows that one of the key resources of the region is the **social capital** in the form of active residents, who want to improve the reality, make the "small homeland" a more liveable place.

With regard to issues of **church** and religious practice, as the historical overview shows, the area was a world of three religions before the Second World War, with the Greek Catholic religion dominating. Today, the Catholic religion has the highest number of adherents, as in the rest of the country. Although the 2021 Census data on religion at poviát level is not yet available, data at voivodeship level is available and it confirms that Catholicism ranks first among adherents of religion. Looking at the census of deaneries, the deaneries in the MAP area are in the Latin rite: Ustrzyki Dolne, Lutowiska and Solina and in the Byzantine-Ukrainian rite: Ustrzyki Dolne. There are churches of Jehovah's Witnesses in Lesko and Ustrzyki Dolne. There are places of religious cult in the MAP area, e.g., the Sanctuary of Our Lady of Bieszczady in Jasień (Ustrzyki Dolne) and historic Orthodox churches, e.g. the Greek Catholic church in Smolnik listed as a UNESCO monument. Due to the lack of data at county level, the topic of religion came up in interviews with MAP members. Most people state that the MAP area is a place where most people follow religious practices. Even if they are not strong believers, going to church on Sunday every week is a kind of ritual that is cultivated. In areas that are further away from the centre, mountainous, more touristic, there is a slightly different, freer climate. An example is the commune of Cisna (Leski poviát) and the commune of Lutowiska (Bieszczadzki poviát), where the **opposition** of these municipalities to the conservatism and traditionalism of the region can be seen from their electoral preferences. Although the right-wing party 'Law and Justice' wins the elections in the region by a large margin (app. 50% of the votes), in the commune of Cisna the representatives of liberal parties won, while in the commune of Lutowiska, although Law and Justice won in the last elections, it did so marginally and gained 29% of the votes, with 26% for the People's Party and 25% for the liberal party.

10. Assets and potentials in the Leski-Bieszczadzki region

The MAP area is a region unique in landscape and nature. This is its great advantage over many other rural areas. It is here that people from all over Poland come to experience the "wild Bieszczady" – unspoilt nature, solitude, silence, peace. The locals themselves say it is a unique place to live. However, there are also quite a few downsides to living here mentioned above.

A huge resource in the region is the **social capital** and the **willingness to get involved in various grassroots initiatives**. This is evidenced by the huge scale of the number of active NGOs and Rural Housewives' Circles for such a sparsely populated area. If we add to this the informal initiatives, neighbourhood meetings and other activities, it becomes a large palette of activities aimed at acting for the benefit of the local community.

Podkarpackie voivodeship is distinguished by one of the highest **number of NGOs per 10 000 inhabitants** – 30 (GUS, 2023). If we apply this value to the MAP area, where the **total number of organisations per 46,216 inhabitants in both poviats amounts to 408**, including rural housewives' associations and foundations, the number is dizzying: **88 organisations per 10 thousand inhabitants!**

The 2023 Piróg et al. (2023) report on the social capital of the Podkarpackie voivodeship shows that the MAP area is unique compared to the other poviats of the voivodeship – it is here that there is **the highest saturation of nonprofit organisations per 10,000 inhabitants in 2016-2022**. Higher values were only recorded in the large cities – Rzeszów and Przemyśl – but this is city-specific. On the other hand, **among rural areas there are no higher indicators than in the Leski and Bieszczadzki counties**. According to this report, the average value for Poland is 2.32, for Podkarpackie it is 2.65 (i.e. higher than the national average), and for the MAP area it is 2x higher, i.e. a range between 4.01 and 5. It is worth adding at that in Poland, 2018 was an important year for the NGO sector, when the **Act on Rural Housewives' Circles** and **the annual subsidies for all registered Circles from the Agency for the Restructuring and Modernisation of Agriculture** came into force. This factor caused an incredible boom of Circles in Poland, but also in the MAP area. In 2018 there were 21 registered Circles, in 2022 - 41, and in 2024 already 50.

Many examples could be given of inspiring activities of the NGO sector in the MAP area. One such positive example is the **activity of the Bieszczady Association "Promyk Nadziei"**, which helps children with disabilities by offering them individual speech therapy, massages and rehabilitation, something that was completely lacking in the MAP area. The founding of the association stemmed from a need for action on the part of parents who themselves have children with disabilities at home and want to provide their children with the best possible conditions for their development. They are also thinking

of setting up a Professional Activity Facility, which would give children and adults with disabilities the chance to get a job and be gainfully employed⁸⁵.

Each commune in the MAP area has a **programme for cooperation with NGOs**. Some communes have outdated programmes and others create them every year and put them out to public consultation. However, finding this information on the communes' websites is mostly not easy. A positive example is the website of the Ustrzyki Dolne commune, where one can find a separate section for NGOs,⁸⁶ and there the programme of cooperation with NGOs, information about competitions, documents and applications, information about the so-called small grants (i.e. grants of up to PLN 10,000, without a competition). Ustrzyki Dolne also stands out from other municipalities in that it is the only one to have: **Civic Budget, Youth Commune Council, Commune Council for Public Benefit Activities** and **NGO coordinator**. Until 2019, the **Bieszczady NGO Forum** was also held in Ustrzyk iDolne.

Bieszczady Women's Forum is also worth mentioning. Its second edition was held in 2024. The creation of the **Women's Council** by active women from the region was also initiated. The initiating members met and discussed the most urgent problems which need to be addressed and pointed out that.

10.1 Social enterprises

According to the government's Social Enterprise Database, there are 8 registered social enterprises in the MAP area, of which 1 is in Leski powiat and 7 in Bieszczadzki powiat. This is the status at the end of December 2023.

Social enterprises in the MAP area are taken care of by POWES (Podkarpackie Social Economy Support Centre) in Jasło, based in Ustrzyki Dolne. A new programming period is currently underway and a new call for grants for social enterprises will be launched in autumn. Therefore, only in autumn will it be known how many of the enterprises listed below will continue to operate. At this point it is worth noting that an organisation that has the status of a social enterprise must maintain a minimum of 3 employees. It can also receive a grant from POWES. In the programming that was coming to an end, this was support in the form of funds for investments and for the first year of operation - also for costs related to employees. In the current call, the support will include measures for the creation of new jobs, reintegration, counselling, coaching or free legal services. From the point of view of businesses, these are worse conditions, as the running costs are high, and no financial support is foreseen in this respect for existing employees.

Examples of social enterprises:

⁸⁵ More information can be found on the association's Facebook page:

https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100064468818988&locale=pl_PL.

⁸⁶ https://ustrzyki-dolne.pl/strona-1568-organizacje_pozarzadowe.html

- Open sp. z o. o. (Stefkowa, Olszanica commune, Leski powiat) - The object of the company's activity is the provision of services for the Olszanica commune. Provided services include primarily cleaning works and care of green areas⁸⁷.
- Bieszczady Sp. z o. o. (Lutowiska, Lutowiska commune, Bieszczadzki powiat) - runs a school canteen in Lutowiska. Provides green area maintenance services, cleaning and minor maintenance work⁸⁸.
- Estro Events Sp. z o. o. (Ustrzyki Dolne, Ustrzyki Dolne commune, Bieszczadzki powiat) - the company is a tourist agent⁸⁹.
- Fundacja "Bieszczadzki Młyn" (Ustrzyki Dolne, Ustrzyki Dolne commune, Bieszczadzki powiat) - the main activity of the Foundation is bread oven baking workshops for tourists and schools, regional cuisine workshops, sale of souvenirs made of flour and baked in the oven⁹⁰.
- Bieszczadzka Foundation (Ustrzyki Dolne, Ustrzyki Dolne commune, Bieszczadzki powiat) - The main activity of the Foundation is running the Green Bike Eco-Travel Office and, until this year, the Czatownia Bistro Cafe⁹¹.
- Bieszczadzka Aniołomania Foundation (Ustrzyki Dolne, Ustrzyki Dolne commune, Bieszczadzki powiat) - Social enterprise engaged in conducting workshops in the field of arts and crafts, production of regional souvenirs from wood and sale of products⁹².
- Konkret Foundation (Ustrzyki Dolne, Ustrzyki Dolne commune, Bieszczadzki powiat) - The main objectives of the Foundation: are activities in the field of providing free legal aid and civic advice and increasing the legal awareness of the society⁹³.
- Lucky-Ski Foundation (Ustjanowa Górna, Ustrzyki Dolne commune, Bieszczadzki powiat) - The Foundation provides accommodation, hippotherapy, horse riding, massage, spa and beauty services and involves excluded people in its activities⁹⁴. The president of the Lucky-Ski Foundation received a national award from the National Institute of Freedom as Volunteer Coordinator for 2022."

In the MAP area, there are many initiatives aimed at integrating residents, involving different groups in activities – social, cultural, educational. They are initiated by non-governmental organisations, local governments and groups of residents not formally associated.

⁸⁷ <http://bazaps.ekonomiaspoleczna.gov.pl/qmina-12-248-1959-olszanica.html>

⁸⁸ <http://bazaps.ekonomiaspoleczna.gov.pl/qmina-12-243-1902-lutowiska.html>

⁸⁹ www.events.estro.org.pl

⁹⁰ <http://mlynbieszczady.pl>

⁹¹ www.fundacjabieszczadzka.org

⁹² www.fundacjabieszczadzka.org

⁹³ www.fundacijakonkret.pl

⁹⁴ http://bazaps.ekonomiaspoleczna.gov.pl/qmina-12-243-1903-ustrzyki_dolne.html

11. Conclusions and potential focus of MAP

The MAP area is unique on the map of Poland, but at the same time it shows various processes as if through a lens, which germinate or not – and it can be a valuable "living lab" for introducing various innovations, also in the field of social economy. These are some of the smallest and least populated communes in Poland, so sometimes, because of the smaller number of people, certain activities can be introduced here more quickly if there is openness to it on the part of, for example, the local government. Where there is good cooperation between NGOs, local government and residents, social capital increases and new interesting initiatives are created. It is influenced by the openness of local leaders to change and by drawing on ideas that have proved successful in others. An example of such municipal management is the commune of Olszanica (Leski powiat), where thanks to multi-sectoral cooperation, thanks to the openness of local authorities to revolution, suddenly from a very indebted commune that was to cease to exist on the administrative map of Poland, where there were no employment prospects, no jobs and no tourist attractions - we have a thriving, tourist-attractive commune. This has happened thanks to the construction of the Bieszczad.Ski Wańkowa⁹⁵ ski complex with a restaurant and hotel right next door. Currently, additional attractions are being built around the resort: the previously mentioned longest tyrolean in Poland, the longest tubing track in the world, a rope park with the longest track in Poland, the rental of 70 mountain electric scooters and there is an idea to create a walking path in the treetops. Residents of the commune become entrepreneurs, starting small businesses, providing accommodation, introducing new services. This has been sparked by the process of revitalising the commune thanks to the support of the European Regional Development Fund and the good cooperation of the local government with NGOs and residents.

The region's greatest wealth, apart from its natural assets, is its **people**. It is thanks to them that local communities change. They are the driving force. It is worth tapping into this enormous resource, supporting and providing the tools and resources for their development.

It should be noted that the beginning of many changes in this particular commune comes from the initiative of Magda and Janusz Demkowicz, the owners of **Bieszczadzkie Drezyny Rowerowe** [Bieszczady Rail Bikes⁹⁶] and **Bieszczadzka Szkoła Rzemiosła**[Bieszczady School of Craft⁹⁷]. They are an example of entrepreneurs who are always ready to cooperate, with a head full of new ideas, whose undertakings are successful on a regional and Polish scale, e.g. the "**Teraz Polska**" [Now Poland] Emblem or a **Tourist Product**. Recently, they were the ones who prepared a new attraction – special **Hulter** downhill scooters, i.e. off-road scooters that can be rented at Bieszczad.Ski Wańkowa.

⁹⁵ <https://bieszczad.ski>

⁹⁶ <https://drezynyrowerowe.pl>

⁹⁷ <https://ginacezawody.pl>

Photo: Iwona Woch

In turn, an example of an NGO that is not afraid of new challenges and cooperates "with everyone" is **the Local Action Group "Zielone Bieszczady"** based in Orelec. As CEO Iwona Woch says *"There are no impossible things. They are only difficult to do" (Alexander The Great)*. On the initiative of this association, a **Co-operation Centre for Sustainable Tourism** was recently established in Stefkowa. The aim of the LAG was to create a place that will be the best showcase of cooperation of various sectors for sustainable development of the LAG "Zielone Bieszczady" LSR area for tourism, recreation and education. The first activities at the site could already be participated in during the picnic on 23.06.2024.

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13. Partners

